

**Optimal Radio Access Technology
Selection and Datarate Allocation in 5G
and Beyond Networks**

A thesis submitted

By

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Dedication

To the blessed souls of my loving, caring, supportive father and darling mother.

Declaration

I, Nurudeen Oladehinbo Salau, assert that this thesis titled: "Optimal Radio Access Technology (RAT) Selection and Datarate Allocation in 5G and Beyond Networks", and the works contained therein are mine. I declare that:

- This work was carried out mainly or entirely while as a candidate for a research degree in this university.
- That no part of this thesis has been previously submitted for a degree or any other professional qualification in this university or any other institution.
- That I have clearly attributed any referenced material or publications.
- Where the work of others has been quoted, the source has always been indicated. Apart from these exceptions, the work in this thesis is entirely mine.
- All main sources of help have also been acknowledged.
- I have also made clear contributions made by myself and others, where part of the work is jointly written with others.

Acknowledgment

I wish to express my gratitude to the Almighty Creator for the gift of life, sound health and sagacity to reach this height. I am also very grateful for the care, nourishment, advice, sacrifice, assistance and prayers of my deceased parents, family members, and friends that have shaped me to this level. My sincere appreciation goes to Prof. Muhammad Zeeshan Shakir; my director of studies, for his motivation, encouragement, help, and supervision. Many thanks to all other research group members and staff of the school of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences, University of the West of Scotland, for their support. I am very grateful to you all.

Abstract

The continuous and exponential number of users in mobile communication, which lead to spectrum saturation called for the exploration of 5G spectrum in Extremely High Frequency (EHF) range. This was done to accommodate the excess devices in form of mobile stations, smartphones, IoT devices, laptops, tablets, palmtops, wearables and other network devices attached to the mobile networks, from the breakthrough recorded in the implementation of full IP, 4G Long Term Evolution (LTE) networks. Meanwhile, the migration of 4G LTE to 5G network for seamless operation, brought about the two architectural designs of 5G network; 5G Non-Stand Alone (NSA), and 5G Stand-Alone (SA), as specified in 3GPP release 15. In 5G NSA, the 5G network still leverages on 4G LTE support, while the 5G SA does not. However, it is recommended that 5G SA networks still run along side 4G SA in Multiple Radio Access Technology (Multi-RAT) scenario, for inter-generation handover. Hence, the choice of a particular network RAT between 5G and 4G LTE in terrestrial communication, which many users depend on becomes imperative. Therefore, the need for optimal RAT selection between these two networks. Many criteria which are mainly user-centric have been considered in literature. However, this research considers both network-centric and user-centric factors in both 5G NSA and 5G SA RAT selection scenarios, for efficient quality of experience (QoE) from users' perspective, and quality of service (QoS) from operators' point of view. Latitude, Longitude, Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), Bandwidth and Data rate were used as criteria to find the appropriate RAT, since mobile users are handed over from one base station to another, based on factors like; geographical location of user, bandwidth requirement and network coverage. It is an open fact, that users that are most impacted as regards RAT selection are the pedestrians and travelling users.

Consequently, the choice of pedestrian in a dense urban region, and mobile user travelling from a sub urban region to urban region in public bus, which have not been used in previous researches in 5G NSA network. Pedestrians and public transport users experience frequent handovers due to mobility; thus, optimising their RAT selection significantly impacts overall network efficiency. Moreover, unlike previous studies, this research effort utilised novel machine learning (ML) techniques, for joint optimisation of RAT selection and data rate allocation, which involved practical methodological rigour of live data validation, and cross-validation metrics, of high significance to users, and quantified improvements to operators.

In the pedestrian scenario with single 5G NSA base station, RAT selection was formulated as a classification process, and further implemented with tree based classification ML algorithms: Decision Tree (DT), Extra Tree (XTREE), Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting (GB), and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) to select the appropriate RAT. Standard classification evaluation metrics, revealed measure of accuracy of DT at 91.82%, RF at 87.64%, XTREE at 86.75%, GB at 91.86%, and XGBoost at 93.86%, respectively. These algorithms were cross-validated for future data, where DT, RF, XTREE, GB and XGBoost recorded 0.909, 0.912, 0.918, 0.918, 0.929 cross-validation score respectively. Observation showed XGBoost has highest performance value, hence adopted as the algorithm for RAT selection.

However, in the 5G NSA multiple base station scenario transversed by a mobile user in public transport bus, RAT selection was carried out by highly rated mobility algorithms: Support Vector Machine (SVM), Deep Neural Network (DNN), and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) as benchmark, to select the appropriate RAT between 4G and 5G RATs. Similarly, evaluation of results with standard classification metrics showed SVM, DNN and XGBoost at 0.8100, 0.9915, and 0.9955 respectively. Results were further cross-validated, where SVM, DNN, and XGBoost showed score values of 0.7293, 0.9906, and 0.9857 respectively. This further justify XGBoost as the suitable ML model, based on its overall outstanding accuracy performance and cross-validation score.

Furthermore, in preparation for the implementation of 5G SA in terrestrial communication terrain, operators and vendors have also begun to equip their products with ML functionalities. Hence, due to challenges related to 5G SA in area of coverage due to high frequency, it is proposed that the 5G SA implementation is run independently with 4G SA networks for inter-RAT fall-over. Therefore, to address the significant challenge in selecting the most suitable RAT for efficient users' experience, this research work proposes a novel solution, that leverages on ML based technique and weighted user association method, to address the complexities associated with these heterogeneous networks. The proposed solution considers factors such as; transmit power of users, location of users, available bandwidth on base stations, number of existing users on base stations, and pathloss between users and base stations, from both users' and networks' perspective. These aforementioned factors are then used as constraints, in an optimisation problem solved by a novel optimiser, to achieve maximised data rate allocation and appropriate RAT selection for users. In contrast to previous researches, the proposed method jointly optimises RAT selection and data rate allocation using ML integrable optimiser. Evaluation of the MILP solver's results with many constraints, revealed a 4% performance increment over Heuristic method's results, with limited constraints and known for its swiftness. The proposed solution was validated with percentage error and standard deviation metrics, which further establish the efficacy of the proposed solution, in improving network performance, users' satisfaction, and resource utilization.

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List of Abbreviations

3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
4G	Forth Generation Cellular Network Technology
5G	Fifth Generation Cellular Network Technology
5GC	5G Core
5GS	5G System
6G	Sixth Generation Cellular Network Technology
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AL	Augmented Lagrangian
AP	Access Point
BBU	Base Band Unit
BS	Base Station
CSI	Channel State Information
CLIP	Column-reduced Integer Programming
CMDP	Constrained Markov Decision Process
CN	Core Network
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
CRAN	Cloud Radio Access Network
DC	Dual Connectivity
DDQN	Double Deep Q Network
DQN	Deep Q Network
DL	Down-link
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning

DT	Decision Tree
EDGE	Enhanced Data Rates for GSM Evolution
EE	Energy Efficiency
EHF	Extremely High Frequency
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broad Band
eNB	Evolved Node B
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
FR1	Frequency Range 1
FR2	Frequency Range 2
GA	Genetic Algorithm
GB	Gradient Boosting
gNB	Next-Generation Node B
GPRS	General Packet Radio Service
HetNets	Heterogeneous Networks
IoT	Internet of Things
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
KNN	K-Nearest Neighbors
LoS	Line of Sight
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MC	Multi-Connectivity
MDP	Markov Decision Process
MEC	Multiaccess Edge-Computing
MIMO	Multiple-Input and Multiple-Output
MILP	Mixed Integer Linear Programming
MINLP	Mixed Integer Nonlinear Programming
ML	Machine Learning
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MM	Mobility Management
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communication

mmWave	Millimeter Wave
MR-DC	Multi-RAT Dual Connectivity
MRM	Multi-RAT Management
MS	Mobile Station
MultiRAT	Multiple Radio Access Technology
NOMA	Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access
NG	New Generation
NR	New Radio
NSA	Non-Standalone
OFDMA	Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiple Access
PSO	Particle Swarm Optimisation
PPP	Poisson Point Processes
QoS	Quality of Service
RA	Resource Allocation
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RF	Random Forest
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RNN	Recurrent Neural Networks
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RRH	Remote Radio Head
RRM	Radio Resource Management
SA	Standalone
SC	Single Connectivity
SCUD	Size-Constrained Community Detection
SINR	Signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio
SDN	Software Defined Network
SLAW	Self-Similar Least Action Walk
SU	System Utility
SVM	Support Vector Machine

UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UDN	Ultra Dense Network
UE	User Equipment
UL	Up-link
UMa	Urban Macro
UMi	Urban Micro
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
USIM	Universal Subscriber Identity Module
V2X	Vehicle-to-Anything
WiFi	Wireless Fidelity
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network
XGBoost	eXtreme Gradient Boosting
XTREE	Extra Tree

Chapter 1

Introduction

The mobile industry has revolutionized the world in barely a decade interval, first with the Frequency Division Multiple Access (FDMA) 1G of 1980s; an analog mobile based technology, meant for voice calls only. The 1G network has an operational frequency of 800 MHz, and data rate of 2.4 kbps [4]. Then, progressively to Time Division Multiple Access / Code Division Multiple Access (TDMA/CDMA); a digital transmission based 2G in the 1990s. Based on its General Packet Radio Service (GPRS), 2G offers a hypothetical total transfer speed of 40 kbps (5 kB/s) [5], whereas, with Enhanced Data Rates for GSM Evolution (EDGE), it has a hypothetical total transfer speed of 384 kbps (48 kB/s) [6]. However, with operational frequencies of 900/1800 MHz, 2G introduced Short Message Service (SMS), email and (Blackberry) chatting services via its GPRS standard. Then, the mobile industry progressed to multimedia based 3G in the 2000s, that offered mobile internet, Global Positioning System (GPS), global roaming facilities and many more, right on our mobile phones. The 3G which was deployed with CDMA transmission, providing a broadband access with data rate between 2-14.4 Mbps, using 2100 MHz operational frequency [7]. This was followed by the Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) based, full IP, 4G LTE in the 2010s. 4G LTE revolutionized the world with mobile audio, High definition (HD) streaming video apps, online gaming, with peak data rate of 200 Mbps. The broadband 4G LTE which operated in sub-6 GHz frequencies range, came with introduction of Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) antennas, as were first specified in 3GPP Release 8 [8], and concept of small cells networks.

Table 1.1: Mobile Telecommunication Generation

Code	Date	Frequency	Technology	Data Rate	Unique Service(s)
1G	1980s	800 MHz	FDMA	2.4kbps	Analogue Voice
2G	1990s	900/1800 MHz	TDMA/CDMA	40/384kbps	SMS, e-mail, (BB) Chatting
3G	2000s	2100 MHz	CDMA	2-14.4Mbps	Mobile Internet, GPS
4G	2010s	Sub-6 GHz	OFDMA	200Mbps (Peak)	Mobile audio, Video Apps
5G	2020s	FR1/FR2	NOMA	20Gbps (Peak)	eMBB, mMTC, URLLC, IoT, Robotics, UAV
6G	2030s	FR3 (Proposed)	NOMA (Proposed)	1Tbps (Peak)	THz comm, Techs Integration via NTN

Hitherto, this evolution as presented in Table 1.1, has only utilized the 700 MHz-2.6 GHz frequency range of the electromagnetic spectrum, which lead to spectrum deficiency in terrestrial communication. Where mobile phones and other wireless devices, for instance laptops and tablets are operating between frequency range of 700 MHz and 6 GHz, with channel bandwidth of 5 to 100 MHz [9]. Hence, the broadband 4G brought about the speedy growth of mobile devices utilisation, and the resultant large data capacity generated thereafter, called for the utilisation of 5G networks spectrum. Consequently, the mobile industry explores the Extremely High Frequency (EHF) band (30-300 GHz), to mitigate the problem associated with resultant heterogeneous networks (HetNets) of myriad devices, with diverse characteristics from the vendor driven 4G LTE.

Progressively, the mobile industry moved into the service driven, full IP, 5G NR (New Radio) in the 2020s, which utilises Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) technology technique. Practically, 5G can operate both in frequency range 1 - FR1 and frequency range 2 - FR2 (millimeter wave (mmWave)) bands: 410 – 7125 MHz, and 24250 – 52600 MHz respectively [10]. It has three ITU-defined applications: Enhanced Mobile Broad Band (eMBB), Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) and Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) [11].

These aforementioned use cases brought about enhanced voice and data communication to maximum data rate of 20 Gbps, interoperability of internet of things (IoT) devices and robotics with mobile communication respectively. The 5G network as implemented today in terrestrial network (TN), is in NSA architectural mode; where 5G networks are supported by 4G LTE networks. Hence, the present 5G implementation with the huge volume of mobile users poses challenges in the choice of RAT selection between 4G and 5G networks, among the base stations available to mobile pedestrians and public transport users (e.g., bus commuters), with respect to their mobility style, location and bandwidth requirement.

Therefore, this research work investigates joint network constraints and user requirements, for suitable RAT selection between 4G LTE and 5G in 5G NSA network, for both pedestrian and travelling users in one hand.

On the other hand, this research further utilises enhanced constraints (available bandwidth, number of existing users on base stations, location of users and pathloss between users and base stations). To form a non-convex, nonlinear optimisation problem, that is further relaxed to a mixed integer linear programming (MILP) problem, for suitable RAT selection and data rate allocation maximisation in 5G SA network, utilising a novel ML based optimiser, in a scenario applicable in 5G advance and 6G era.

1.1 Motivation

The 5G networks have been proposed to be co-deployed with existing technologies in a Multi-RAT fashion, up till moment, the 5G deployments in terrestrial communication depend on support from existing 4G LTE networks, in both stand-alone (SA) and non-stand-alone (NSA) setups. NSA rely on the infrastructure of 4G LTE networks, which might affect mobile subscriber's experience, due to fixed inter-wiring between their base stations [12]; i.e., next generation NodeB (gNB) of 5G and evolved NodeB (eNB) of 4G LTE. On the contrary, SA which is characterized with simple management is rather implemented with inter-generation handover between 5G and 4G LTE.

Therefore, in the current and nearest future of mobile communication implementation, 5G will co-exist with different technologies like 4G in a Multi-RAT environment [13, 14]. Hence, the first main motivation of this research work on RAT selection between 4G LTE and 5G NR RATs. Consequently, the need for matching users to the most appropriate RAT (4G/5G), for effective and efficient performance of the mobile network, which is expected to provide the expected QoS on the part of mobile operators and corresponding QoE on the part of mobile users.

Furthermore, the rapid increment of traffic across the mobile networks, which called for exploration of new spectrum bands of 5G networks, has brought about a quantum growth in the volume of mobile phone subscriptions worldwide; as presented in Fig. 1.1. The amazing figure of mobile phone subscriptions at present, is estimated at 8.9 billion worldwide, which has transcended the current total world population of 8.2 billion people [15]. Since all traffic still passes through the existing RATs of 5G NR and underlying 4G LTE, this necessitates dynamic RAT selection in 4G/5G Multi-RAT networks, using a framework which can dynamically adjust to varying network conditions and mobile user preferences, and ensuring optimal RAT selection in real-time. Hence, the adoption of ML in this research, in order to attain a fast selection scheme, which can guarantee effective resource allocation between 4G LTE and 5G NR RATs.

1.2 Research Aim and Objectives

The main aim of this study is to design and implement a unique technique that will accomplish appropriate RAT selection and data rate allocation in both existing 5G NSA, and yet to be implemented 5G SA networks in terrestrial network environs, in order to obtain efficient and effective resource allocation. Hence, the objectives of the research are:

- Design system level approach for the analysis of 5G network by considering joint user-network requirements, in relation with quality of experience and quality of services.

Figure 1.1: Statistics of mobile (cellular) subscriptions worldwide from 1993 to 2023 [1].

- Develop and implement RAT selection algorithm, by considering user-network constraints: geographical location, mobility style, bandwidth requirement and network coverage, in 5G NSA networks for both pedestrian and travelling users.
- Formulate multi-objective optimization problem, in a 5G SA architecture scenario, in order to maximise data rate of users, relative to their location and respective transmit power. Implement solution to resolve the optimisation problem using a novel ML based optimiser, with consideration to the following criteria: available bandwidth, number of existing users on base stations, location of users and pathloss between users and base stations, for appropriate RAT selection and data rate maximisation for users, in order to achieve efficient and effective resource allocation.

1.3 List of Publications

Below is a list of peer-reviewed **Conference papers**, **Journal papers**, and **Chapter contribution**, the researcher has presented, showcasing his humble contribution to the field of knowledge, with details of publications and publishers.

- **Peer-reviewed Conference Papers**

[1] N.O. Salau, M. Z. Shakir, "Machine learning enabled multi-radio access technology selection in 5G networks- SICSA Conference 2022: Sustainability, Recovery and Resilience, 2022.

[2] N. O. Salau and M. Z. Shakir, "Machine learning analysis of multi-radio access technology selection in 5g nsa network," in 2023 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC), 2023, pp. 1–6.

- **Peer-reviewed Journal Papers**

[1] N. Salau, S. Manzoor, and M. Shakir, "Machine learning approach of multi-rat selection for travelling users in 5g nsa networks." *IET Netw*, vol. 1–11, 2024.

[2] N. Salau, S. Al-Ahmed., S. Manzoor, and M. Shakir "Machine Learning Enabled Optimal RAT Selection and Data rate Allocation in 5G SA and Beyond" *EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, (Submitted).

- **Chapter Contribution**

[1] N. Salau, and M. Shakir, "Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN): A vital component of 6G framework for universal ubiquitous and continuous connectivity. *Elsevier*, November 2024.

1.4 Organisation of the Thesis

The Fig. 1.2 provides an overview of the thesis structure showing the relationship among the chapters. A summary of the chapters is therefore given below:

Chapter 1 presents the motivation behind this research, its aim and objectives, as well as my publications and humble contributions to the field of knowledge.

Chapter 2 gives an overview of 5G technology; the 5G architectural designs, 5G Use cases, 5G spectrum, as well as 5G key performance indicators (KPIs). It further presents the literature review carried out to determine the system level approach adopted for the research. The literature review showcases a summary of previous published works, related to this research. It is used to identify gaps and hence, assist in raising research questions after the researcher has examined the breadth of knowledge in the field of study. Hence, problem statements are stated, with proposed ML solutions. Moreover, the research methodology details general methodological procedures followed to achieve the stated objectives. Emphasising the joint user-network requirements, needed for the successful implementation of RAT selection in 5G networks. These requirements are in consideration with respect to quality of experience and quality of services respectively.

Chapter 3 presents machine learning analysis of Multi-Radio Access Technology selection in 5G NSA network, to address the first objective. Where the study examines joint user requirements and network constraints for suitable RAT selection between 4G LTE and 5G NR for a pedestrian user, utilizing a 5G NSA base-station. Numerical results reveal that the proposed ML algorithm achieves outstanding performance relative to referenced algorithms, and guarantees better measure of accuracy and validation. This addresses the second objective of the thesis from a pedestrian user's perspective.

Chapter 4 however, presents study that addresses the second objective: machine learning approach of Multi-RAT selection for travelling users in 5G NSA networks. Unlike the previous chapter that addresses the first objective, with a pedestrian using 5G NSA base station. This chapter takes the study further by considering a bus travelling user utilizing multiple 5G NSA base stations, which has not been used in literature.

The appropriate RAT selections are carried out, with respect to user's location, bandwidth requirement, mobility style and network coverage. Similarly, numerical results also record outstanding measure of accuracy and validation, when the proposed algorithm is compared with the referenced ones. This completely achieves the second objective of the thesis.

Chapter 5 in its own case, presents machine learning enabled optimal RAT selection and data rate allocation in 5G SA and beyond networks, to address the third objective. Here, a novel ML enabled solution is utilised to solve an optimisation problem, in a typical 5G SA architecture scenario, with multiple base stations serving multiple users, in order to maximise data rate of users, relative to their location and respective transmit power. Simulation results show that the proposed optimisation problem solver is close to the optimal solution offered by Heuristic method. Although the constraints considered, introduced complexity, thus making the optimisation problem a non-convex, nonlinear type. However, it is easily solved by the proposed mixed integer linear programming (MILP) optimiser. Hence, guaranteeing appropriate base station RAT selection and users' data rate allocation, which are required for efficient network bandwidth utilisation. Making it a promising application in 5G SA and beyond networks deployment. This achieves the third objective of the thesis.

Chapter 6 finally features the overall conclusion of the research described in this thesis. The contributions are summarised, followed by suggestions regarding directions of future research. A high-level proposal of dynamic RAT selection in 6G terrestrial network (TN) and non-terrestrial network scenarios is presented as a form of future work.

1.5 Chapter Summary

This chapter presents the motivation, aim, and objectives of this research work. It also highlights the publications of the researcher and the organization of this thesis. However, the next chapter gives an overview of the research; detailing the 5G architectures, its use cases, spectrum allocation in 5G, the 6G technology enablers, key performance indicators (KPIs) comparison of 5G and 6G etc., as well as literature review of this research effort.

Figure 1.2: Thesis structure showing the summary of the chapters.

Chapter 2

Research Overview and Literature

Review

2.1 Introduction

The fifth generation of mobile network; 5G or 5GS standard, as defined by 3GPP in Release 15 [16], covers the following: air interface, protocols and network interfaces that enable the whole 5G architecture mobile system [17]. However, schematically, the 5G system as depicted in Fig. 2.1, comprises: User Equipment (UE), the New Generation Radio Access Network (NG-RAN) and the Core Network (5GC). The UE comprises of Mobile Station (MS) and Universal Subscriber Identity Module (USIM) card, meant for user's authentication and accessing network.

The 5G base station, as shown in Fig. 2.1, is a major component of the NG-RAN, denoted gNB. Where "g" connotes "5G" and "NB" stands for "Node B", which refers to the radio transmitter of the base station. The radio interface is called "NR-Uu", where "NR" stands for "New Radio", i.e., "5G". Uu is the radio interface that connects the user equipment (UE) to the Terrestrial Radio Access Network (NG-RAN). The 5GC is however, pictorially represented by the Access and Mobility management Function (AMF) and User Plane Function (UPF) in (AMF/UPF) entity. The UPF handles user's data, while in the signalling plane, whereas the AMF accesses the UE and the RAN.

Figure 2.1: Overview of fifth generation (mobile communication) system - 5GS.

2.1.1 Non-Standalone 5G Architecture

In 5G implementation, there are two main deployment options: the 5G NSA and 5G SA architectures. 5G NSA architecture is a migration setup towards the full 5G SA deployment. In 5G NSA, as shown in Fig. 2.2, the 5G access network is connected to the 4G Core Network; EPC. In this design, the 4G LTE base station; eNB connects to the 5G NR base station; gNB via the X2 interface. The X2 interface is used to connect two eNBs, and it also supports eNB and gNB connection in 5G NSA architecture as shown in Fig. 2.2. Hence, 5G NSA can provide dual connectivity, through the 4G E-UTRAN and the 5G NR. Therefore, referred to as "EN-DC", which stands for "E-UTRAN and NR Dual Connectivity".

Practically, in a simplified block diagram illustration, as shown in Fig. 2.3. 5G NSA architecture combines multiple RATs by interworking with the existing 4G LTE network [12]. That is, 5G NR radio cells are mixed with 4G LTE radio cells using dual connectivity (DC). To offer radio access that can provide higher mobile broadband speeds, before connection to the core network (EPC) of 4G LTE. In 5G NSA, 4G LTE radio cells are used primarily for the control plane, while 5G NR radio cells are used for user plane.

Hence, 5G NSA mobile network RATs are basically deployed as a mixture of LTE and NR in a Multi-RAT fashion.

Figure 2.2: The 5G non-standalone (NSA) architecture.

It is developed to address the exponential growth in traffic demand, along with myriad and heterogeneous universal mobile devices estimated to increase from 8.8 billion in 2018 to 13.1 billion by 2023. 1.4 billion of which will be 5G capable [18]. Its operation is within the frequency range (FR1); 410 MHz-7125 MHz [12].

2.1.2 Standalone 5G Architecture

In 5G SA however, as shown in Fig. 2.4, 5G access network is connected to the 5G Core Network; (5GC). The 5G NR base station; gNB connects to each other via the Xn interface. However, the gNB connects to the 5G core via NG interface. Hence, the 5G SA, is a pure end-to-end 5G network, and it uses only one RAT, to connect to the core network; 5GC. That is; the 5G NR radio cells are used for both control plane and user plane, as depicted in Fig. 2.5. Typically, the 5G SA system comprises of the user equipment (UE), the Radio Access Network (RAN); tagged New Radio (NR), and the 5G core (5GC).

Figure 2.3: Block diagram of 5G non-standalone (NSA) architecture.

The 4G SA system however, comprises of the user equipment (UE), the Radio Access Network (RAN); tagged LTE, and the 4G core; EPC. 5G SA equipments access 5GC with control signalling independent of 4G network, and accomplish interoperability between 4G and 5G networks via their core networks. This is used to implement inter-RAT handover and/or redirection depending on different use cases with less latency [19].

Summarily, comparing 5G NSA, with 5G SA, 5G SA has a separate core and radio network, whereas 5G NSA entails deploying 5G RAN on top of existing 4G LTE infrastructure. Hence, 5G SA displays precedence in End-to-End (E2E) latency, uplink (UL), and edge computing. Therefore, it offers better user experience, delivers contents in real time, supports augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) applications. Consequently, the research studies cover both 5G NSA and SA architectures. Table 2.1 presents details of NSA and SA features in 5G technology [19] [18].

Figure 2.4: The 5G standalone (SA) architecture.

Figure 2.5: Block diagram of 5G standalone (SA) architecture.

Table 2.1: Comparison between 5G non-stand alone (NSA) and 5G stand alone (SA)

Parameter	5G NSA	5G SA
BaseStation	eNB	gNB
RAT	NR + LTE	NR
Core	EPC or 5GC	5GC
Control	LTE	NR
Data	NR	NR
Userplane latency	10 - 20 ms	<1 ms
Controlplane latency	10 - 20 ms	10 - 20 ms
Spectrum	DSS	NR
Application	eMBB	eMBB, mMTC, uRLLC
Downlink	100 Mbps	NR
Uplink	5 Mbps	NR
Voice	VoLTE	EPS fallback or VoNR
Multiplexing	TDD	TDD
Backhaul	5 Mbps	NR
Reliability	5 Mbps	99.999%

2.2 Use Cases of 5G Networks

The current generation of mobile communication 5G networks, based on the 3GPP Release 15 standard, supports three ITU-defined important use cases: enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), massive machine type communication (mMTC), and ultra-reliable low latency communications (URLLC). The eMBB focuses on enhanced voice and data communication of 10-20 Gbps maximum data rate, 50-100 Mbps user experience data rate and 4ms one-way latency in user plane [19]. The mMTC addresses interoperability with internet of things (IoT) devices, URLLC however, is concerned with ultra high availability, ultra high reliability, and low latency connection use case, as required, for instance, in robotics application.

2.3 Spectrum Allocation in 5G

The 5G networks are explored due to their huge spectrum allocation, and high frequency band, especially in the mmWave region (above 24 GHz), that is also distinguished with high attenuation, that called for the application of massive MIMO and beam steering for directionality. Consequently, the sub division of 5G frequencies of operation into sub-1 GHz (coverage layer), 1-6 GHz (capacity layer), and above 6 GHz (high throughput layer) [12].

Therefore, 5G networks, will be deployed as mixed sub-6 GHz and mmWave, in Multi-RAT and Ultra Dense Network (UDN) fashion. Thus, its frequency of operations are categorised as lower frequencies; frequency range 1 (FR1) band: 410–7125 MHz, and higher frequencies; frequency range 2 (FR2) - millimeter Wave (mmWave) band: 24250–52600 MHz. FR1 (410 MHz-7125 MHz) overlaps with 4G frequencies, reason for its adoption in 5G NSA.

However, the 5G SA, is expected to utilise the FR2 (24250 MHz–52600 MHz); mmWave band, and Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) transmission technique, to address challenging voice, data, application and heterogeneous network (HetNet) issues of myriad devices. mmWave 5G networks are ultra-fast, hence, they are ultra-short range. mmWave wavelengths generally is between 1 to 10 mm, and located within the Extremely High Frequency (EHF) band 30-300 GHz. Table 2.2 displays the 5G spectrum coverage, capacity and some application.

2.4 Key Performance Indicators of 5G Networks

Primarily, the 5G technology is meant to address terrestrial coverage challenges (i.e., spectrum crunch). Hence, following the use cases and assigned frequencies of operation, the 5G is bench-marked with the following key performance indicators (KPIs) as presented in Table 2.3 [3].

The 5G is expected to have a peak (maximum) data rate of 20 Gbps for pedestrian, while its real experienced data rate is rated 100 Mbps or 0.1 Gbps. Also, 5G is rated with super high peak spectral efficiency of about 30 bits/sec/Hz.

Table 2.2: 5G Spectrum Coverage, Capacity and Application

Parameter	Sub-6 Ghz	mmWave
Frequency	< 6 GHz	24-100 GHz
Wavelength	10-100 mm	1-10 mm
Bandwidth	Average	Ultra- High
Coverage	High	Low
Capacity	Average	High
Throughput	High	Ultra-High
Latency	Low	Very low (<1 ms)
Environ	Rural/Urban	Dense Urban
Bandwidth	50-100 MHz	1 GHz
Pathloss	High	Very high
Application	V2N	V2V

Meanwhile, 5G real experienced spectral efficiency is evaluated at 0.3 bits/sec/Hz. With a maximum bandwidth of 1 GHz, 5G will record a super-real-time area traffic capacity of 10 Mb/s/m^2 for connectivity. In addition, 5G is projected with ubiquitous connection density of about 1 million (10^6) devices/ km^2 for dense urban coverage. The latency of 5G, which is considered less than 1 ms, coupled with evaluated reliability of about $1-10^{-5}$, the 5G technology, will ensure the promising amazing data throughput, and UE low battery consumption, to meet up with service providers and mobile users.

2.4.1 Sixth Generation of Mobile Communication

The 6G is the sixth generation of mobile communication in hierarchy after 5G. It is a digital, full IP, full duplex, broadband wireless standard, that has been postulated may utilise the NOMA technique as access method, and FR3 (7.125 GHz - 24.25 GHz) band for frequency operation. 6G; with a projected peak data rate of 1Tbps [3] [20], will establish a new three-dimensional paradigm, with space–airborne–terrestrial conglomeration.

Table 2.3: 5G Key Performance Indicators

KPI	5G
Peak data rate	20 Gbps
Experienced data rate	0.1 Gbps
Peak spectral efficiency	30 bits/s/Hz
Experienced spectral efficiency	0.3 bits/s/Hz
Maximum bandwidth	1 GHz
Area traffic capacity	10 Mb/s/m ²
Connection density	10 ⁶ devices/km ²
Latency	1 ms
Reliability	1-10 ⁻⁵

The 6G introduces the following emerging technologies or enablers to achieve its goal:

- **New Spectrum - Terahertz (THz) Communications**

Terahertz frequency technically connotes electromagnetic waves within frequencies range 100 GHz - 10 THz, and wavelengths 30 μm - 3 mm. However, the THz bands 275 GHz - 3 THz are stipulated to be used for cellular communications, as specified by international telecommunication union (ITU) [21] [22].

- **Ultra-Massive Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (UM-MIMO) Antennas**

Part of the challenges of THz band communications are short communication distances, high propagation losses, and power limitations. Hence, UM-MIMO antenna designs have been developed as feasible solutions to address these challenges [21] [22], which will eventually enhance overall system capacity.

- **Holographic Beamforming**

This technique permits several simultaneous transmissions with the use of same frequency without interference, thus allowing continuous reuse the same band of frequencies to render high intensity signals to mobile and stationary users, within a given spatial region [21].

- **Joint Communications and Sensing (JCAS)**

This is the amalgamation of sensing functionalities into the fabric of wireless communication technology i.e., joint design and co-location of wireless communication and sensing (C&S) systems. For instance, incorporation of intelligent vehicular networks and the IoT (Internet of Things) in one system, to reduce device size, costs and power consumption, using a single transmitted signal.

- **Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence**

Machine learning (ML); is a subset of artificial intelligence (AI). It has been proposed for signal processing in 6G, to learn the entire communications system model and train a special kind of neural network (autoencoder) [22], to allow modification of the signal to be transmitted. Also, AI and ML have been projected to manage security threats and privacy challenges, that might arise, due to the volume of myriad devices that will be connected to the 6G network, by securing its gateways and endpoints.

- **Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs)**

RIS is a technology used to manage electromagnetic waves that pass through the radio propagation channel via metamaterials, whose characteristics allow control of ways their surfaces reflect electromagnetic (EM) waves, from microwaves through the visible range. Hence, by enabling explicit control of its subwavelength unit cells, a metamaterial can become programmable and thus reconfigurable [21], this permits network operators to control the random radio environment.

- **Photonics-Visible Light Communications**

Photonics refers to the physical science of light waves, which includes generation, detection and manipulation of light. Lately, photonics project prospect for designing systems and manufacturing of integrated circuits related devices, that can be used for different applications in advanced sensing, high-speed data communications, and imaging in relation to 6G era. Meanwhile, Visible Light Communication (VLC) is a general term which encompasses the transmission of data over free space or fibre, using light sources like LEDs, laser diodes emitting at visible wavelengths.

- **Quantum Communication**

Quantum communication is an aspect of applied quantum physics, used in safeguarding information channels from eavesdropping via quantum cryptography. It creates opportunity of envisioning extremely high data rates, reduced computational complexity, and cyber-security requirements [23], in the 6G and beyond era.

- **Full-Duplex Communications**

The present mobile communication standards (e.g., 4G, 5G), employ time division duplex (TDD) and frequency division duplex (FDD) communication standards, and can operate in half and full-duplex modes. In half-duplex communication, the transmission and reception are not performed at the same time or frequency [3]. Meanwhile, 6G will use full-duplex or inband full-duplex (IBFD) technology, that allows a device to transmit and receive concurrently in the same frequency band. This 6G characteristic accounts for its projected double spectral efficiency and tremendous increase in its throughput.

- **Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs)**

Non-terrestrial networks, consist of space-borne; (i.e, satellite constellation), and airborne networks (i.e, High-Altitude Platform Stations (HAPS), Air-To-Ground (ATG), Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs)), meant to compliment existing terrestrial networks, in order to enhance radio access capability, bridge the digital divide, and provide ubiquitous 3D connectivity across the globe.

2.4.2 Key Performance Indicators of 6G network

Primarily, the 5G technology is meant to address terrestrial coverage challenges (i.e., spectrum crunch), while 6G is coming up to address global coverage connectivity. However, as proposed and presented in many literature, for example in [3] and [20], the 6G key performance indicators (KPIs) requirements are greater than those of 5G. Hence, as presented in Table 2.4, 6G is envisioned to deliver at peak (maximum) data rate of 1 Tb/s, that is 100 times greater than the 5G of peak (maximum) data rate 20 Gb/s. Also, 6G is postulated to have a 1 Gb/s experienced data rate, while 5G is rated 100 Mb/s or 0.1 Gb/s.

Table 2.4: Comparison of 5G and 6G Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) [3]

KPI	5G	6G
Peak data rate	20 Gb/s	1 Tb/s
Experienced data rate	0.1 Gb/s	1 Gb/s
Peak spectral efficiency	30 bits/s/Hz	60 bits/s/Hz
Experienced spectral efficiency	0.3 bits/s/Hz	3 bits/s/Hz
Maximum bandwidth	1 GHz	100 GHz
Area traffic capacity	10 Mb/s/m ²	1 Gb/s/m ²
Connection density	10 ⁶ devices/km ²	10 ⁷ devices/km ²
Energy efficiency	not specified	1 Tb/J
Latency	1 ms	100 μ s
Reliability	1-10 ⁻⁵	1-10 ⁻⁹
Jitter	Not specified	1 μ s

In addition, the peak spectral efficiency of 6G is proposed to be at 60 bits/sec/Hz, while 5G is rated 30 bits/sec/Hz. Meanwhile, their real experienced spectral efficiency are valued at 3 bits/s/Hz and 0.3 bits/s/Hz respectively. Furthermore, the 6G technology bandwidth is proposed to be 100 GHz, which is also 100 times higher than the maximum bandwidth of 5G rated at 1 GHz. The 6G area traffic capacity is estimated at 1 Gb/s/m², while 5G traffic capacity is estimated at 10 Mb/s/m². Likewise, the 6G connection density is expected to increase more than 10 times than that of 5G, i.e., over 10 million (10⁷) devices/km² for the 6G, while 5G is expected to support about 1 million (10⁶) devices/km². 6G end-to-end latency is valued to be at about 100 μ s, this is 100 times lower than 5G latency rated 1 ms. With evaluated reliability of 1-10⁻⁹ and 1-10⁻⁵ for 6G and 5G respectively, it should be noted that from the stated KPIs, partial prerequisite can only be satisfied at specified 6G use case [20].

2.4.3 Use Cases of 6G Network

Use cases suggest specific situation or scenario in which a product, solution or service could potentially be applied. Hence, the following use cases among others are proposed or suggested for 6G network as presented in Fig. 2.6, which is envisioned for diverse services in telecommunication, automation, transportation, healthcare, agriculture and many more.

- **Digital Twinning**

This highlights the application of 6G in digital twinning in building models, manufacturing sector, immersive smart cities and disaster relief digital twin for public protection.

- **3D Mobility Networks**

This is part of the requirements to be addressed by 6G network, which has to do with network assisted 3D mobility, for wide area surveillance or monitoring as well as environmental radio sensing.

- **Cobots and Autonomous Robots**

This is the use case for collaborative robots otherwise known as cobots, applicable in flexible manufacturing environment in 6G era, which is line with industry 4.0 standard. It also addresses autonomous robots like self driving bicycles and cars, unmanned aerial vehicles and the likes, that require the 6G support for effectiveness.

- **Seamless Immersible Experience**

This use case supports virtual, mixed, augmented reality (VR/MR/AR) applications [3], e.g., immersive reality for educational purpose, sports and game events, that also require high data rates expected to be provided by 6G network.

- **Extremely High Capacity Backhaul**

This use case points to high data rate wireless infrastructure (1 Tbps transport), that will serve as a support to the optical fiber infrastructure in outdoor and indoor deployments, to prevent any challenges in the backhaul (or xHaul) [3].

- **Sustainability**

This has to do with the application of 6G in E-health, sustainable food production in agriculture, earth monitoring and many more.

- **Trusted Embedded Environments** This use case concerns, the human-centric networks, that has to do with sensor infrastructure web [21], which include industrial sensors networks for safe production in manufacturing sector, interconnected IoT micro-networks, AI-enabled vehicle-to-everything (V2X), e.t.c.

- **Global Connectivity**

Bridging the digital gap is part of the purpose of enhancement of application of NTN in 6G era, due to the fact that, so many lonely areas, isolated regions, oceans, e.t.c, are not covered by the terrestrial infrastructure.

Figure 2.6: Use cases of sixth generation mobile communication (6G) network.

2.5 Literature Review

The proliferation of mobile subscribers UE, and the 3GPP radio technologies standards such as; RATs of 5G-NR and underlying 4G (LTE), require radio resources allocation management for each RAT based on RAT capability information. Since, each radio technology is treated individually as a separate entity in terms of radio access, hence, each UE controls its own access to the wireless network.

However, a UE may operate in multiple modes and hence, support Multi-RATs. For example, a LTE device may also support 5G NR. Similarly, a 5G NR device may also support LTE RAT.

In view of the above, depending on how a RAT is selected, and how the usage of available RATs are managed, the UE and the wireless network may not produce the best results in terms of resource allocation management, this can negatively impact the UE. Hence the need for an efficient RAT selection scheme, that can assure effective resource allocation management.

Therefore, to accomplish this challenge, the researcher engaged in literature review of past similar researches. The first step taken was to identify what had been done related to RAT selection, from past to present generation of cellular system. Then, relevant papers were selected and organised into themes. Finally, a summary of the main findings was compiled and written. Consequently, to address the issues related to RAT selection, the researcher discovered many papers have been published, based on researches that have been carried out in the past. Table 2.5 summarises representative studies on RAT selection, selected based on their focus on 4G/5G interworking, methodology in (RL/game theory vs. ML), and use of simulated vs. live data. Key limitations are highlighted to contextualise key contributions. Hence, these research efforts will be elucidated in this thesis, based on their relevance.

For instance in [24], a RAT selection system of multi-connectivity (MC) configuration has been proposed. Where authors adopted distributed reinforcement learning (RL), so that each device can study its policy for effective MC configuration and choose appropriate RATs. Authors claimed simulation results showed 20.8% reliability improvements over single connectivity (SC) scheme. However, unlike supervised learning, where the data is labeled, RL agents have to interact with their environment and use different actions to obtain the optimal policy. In a complex and dynamic scenario, this will waste time, and thereby making RL costly. Also, in [25], probabilistic user association that lead to a non-convex problem, was formulated to find solution for suitable RAT between WiFi and 4G technologies, which eventually require computationally tasking geometric approach to accomplish.

Similarly in [26], matching game theory has been adopted for RAT selection between LTE and Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) RATs technologies. Meanwhile using game theories according to [27] are typically complexity-prohibitive, and their convergence to the optimal solution is not guaranteed.

Likewise in [27], the authors developed a network selection scheme for resource allocation over heterogeneous networks using latency, cost, and energy consumption, as parameters to be optimized in a WiFi/cellular network scenario only, this is in contrast to this study that utilises 4G and 5G networks.

Moreover in [28], a ML based RAT selection was implemented in the Internet of Moving Things (IoMT), where four algorithms: Naive Bayes, multi-layer perceptron, decision tree (DT) and K-Nearest Neighbour (K-NN), are implored, the authors chose DT algorithm for RAT selection as the most efficient among others. It is observed that these previous RAT selection techniques were carried out in one single network 5G or 4G/WiFi or 5G/WiFi. Hence, the peculiarity of this study that utilises 5G NR and underlying 4G LTE networks. This study also considers Geo-location of UE (longitude and latitude) and RSSI which were not used in previous works as basic parameters. These parameters are uniquely measured from a live network of 5G NSA base-station unlike simulated ones from previous works.

Hence, DT implementation is used as a benchmark model, in comparison with RAT selection implementation of other standard classification ML algorithms; Extra Tree (XTREE), Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting (GB), and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), which existing literature suggests have not been used for RAT selection in the existing literature. The results indicated that XGBoost showed the highest computational speed, model performance accuracy, and also showed its ability to eliminate the overfitting problem associated with DT adopted by [28], when handling very large data. This study has been published and fully presented in Chapter 4 of this thesis.

Furthermore, in order to address the second objective, related to a travelling user, transversing multiple 5G NSA base stations, some relevant researches from findings have also been published. For example in [29], a 5G multi-layered radio access network (RAN) selection scheme, that considered the direction of movement of user equipment (UE) and

the location of the researcher cells has been proposed. The scheme utilized the velocity of UE and type of cell for connection, to reduce the number of handovers.

However, the authors considered 5G network RANs alone and also neglected bus-traveling users, rather considered pedestrian and car users only in their simulation.

Likewise, the authors in [30], developed a deep ML model based on gated recurrent neural networks (RNN). That uses a sequence of previous beams of serving base station, to predict the most likely base station a mobile user will next connect with. To address reliability, and latency challenges during coordination among multiple base stations in millimeter wave (mmWave) wireless systems. The authors only considered a car mobile user moving at random speeds, within a 160m street, served by two mmWave base stations in their simulation.

Also in [31], a convolutional neural networks (CNN) based approach, to predict the mobile traffic of base stations had been proposed. The authors leveraged on collected 4G mobile data in highway scenarios only, using the data rate and longitude of seven base stations. These are in contrast with our live collected data from intra-city public transport system, and utilization of both 4G and 5G RATs in 5G NSA scenario, with consideration to latitude, longitude, data rate experience of the user, as well as RSSI and bandwidth of 47 base stations as parameters. Meanwhile, CNN requires a lot of training data, and usually fails to encode the position and orientation of objects.

Similarly in [32], the authors proposed a Multi-RAT mobility management (MM) algorithm. Where network topology, radio frequency (RF) conditions, and discount factors were used as parameters, for appropriate RAT selection. The proposed system was modeled as a Markov decision process (MDP), to guide the handover policy between 4G and 5G RATs. However, the authors did not address radio resource management (RRM) issues, and they utilized the MDP approach type of reinforcement learning.

In addition in [33], a pricing-based network selection scheme to address traffic allocation issues in dense Multi-RAT had been proposed. Where dynamic decisions of network controller-defined policy, pricing, and congestion control the decisions of UEs in directing their traffic through available RATs.

Although the authors considered WiFi, 3G, 4G, and 5G-NR networks in their simulation, they utilised a proportionally fair bandwidth allocation process, instead of artificial intelligence (AI) or ML algorithms for RAT selection decisions.

Furthermore in [34], a software defined network (SDN)/ML-based scheme referred to as; K-nearest neighbor (A2T-KNN) algorithm has been proposed. To address handover between conventional high-powered macro and low-powered small base stations, in millimeter wave (mmWave) based heterogeneous networks (HetNets) in London. HetNet features and UE movement information were used as parameters for a KNN model, that was trained based on generated vehicle and base station information. Although the authors' simulation was based on a two-tier setup, they restricted their study to mmWave only and utilized KNN; one of the weakest predictive ML algorithm.

Lately in [35], an online RAT selection algorithm in a 5G Multi-RAT network, using Constrained Markov Decision Process (CMDP) - a reinforcement based algorithm, was proposed, to address sub-optimal utilization of network resources. Several networks, channel conditions, and priority of users were used as criteria for RAT selection between 5G-NR and Wireless Fidelity (WiFi) networks; an offloading process, in an NS-3 simulated approach, unlike inter-generational handover between 4G and 5G in a live scenario RAT selection.

Also, recently in [36], a 5G Multi-RAT URLLC and eMBB dynamic task offloading with multiaccess edge-computing (MEC) resource allocation using distributed deep reinforcement learning (DRL) had been proposed, to address Quality-of-Service (QoS) requirement. The authors proposed UE to make optimal offloading decisions, while the MEC server dynamically adjusts the server resources based on offloading requests, from multiple UEs using DRL technology. To minimize the energy consumption of the UEs, while maximizing the system utility (SU) performance. However, DRL has high computational cost, because its models often involve a large number of parameters and require massive amounts of data to train effectively.

Similarly in [37], a 5G non-standalone (NSA) mode, a traffic steering mechanism based on deep Q-learning, was adopted. To maintain a seamless user experience by choosing appropriate RAT (5G or LTE) dynamically.

The proposed method was compared with a heuristic-based algorithm, and Q-learning-based traffic steering, for load-balancing purposes. The authors reported success in an optimal way, as whenever the high load is induced to a particular RAT, traffic is steered to another RAT dynamically. However, in deep Q-Learning, the Q-function is typically non-linear and can have many local minima. This can make it difficult for the neural network to converge to the correct Q-function.

Furthermore, leveraging on the Multi-RAT facilities, in [38], a regional Multi-RAT dual connectivity management for reliable 5G Vehicle-to-Anything (V2X) communications was carried out, based on release 16 of the Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) standards for V2X specifications. The authors presented Multi-RAT dual connectivity (MR-DC) aware, regional Multi-RAT management (MRM) entity, for reliability improvement of 5G V2X through the use of redundant transmissions.

Moreover, in [39], Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) were researched in different areas and diverse use cases for UAV parcel transport in an emergency service. The facilities of 4G and 5G networks technology in Multi-RAT architecture were used, as an alternative solution for scenarios, where the 5G network is unstable or not yet fully deployed. Authors conclusion showed that the 5G network can provide the necessary QoS for UAV operations, even at low received signal power in the order of -90 , unlike 4G network which although has a reliable link but can not provide the required latency as 5G.

Consequently, in [40], a comparative analysis of four superior mobility predictors: Deep Neural Network (DNN), extreme Gradient Boosting Trees (XGBoost), Semi-Markov and Support Vector Machine (SVM) had been done. A synthetic dataset of eighty-four mobile users, generated using the self-similar least action walk (SLAW) mobility model, was used to predict the future location of mobile users. The authors used an LTE simulator to generate the network topology of seven macro cells and rated XGBoost the highest in performance.

Hence, in furtherance to the previous study on RAT selection by a pedestrian, which utilized a single base station [10], where XGBoost was also rated with utmost performance. The XGBoost is hereby used as a benchmark model in the second study, then RAT implementation is further carried out with classification algorithms:

DNN-(Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) type), and SVM. Using data rate along with Geolocation of UE (longitude and latitude), RAT bandwidth, and RSSI, which were uniquely measured from live network of 5G NSA base-stations, unlike simulated ones in literature as basic parameters. Based on existing literature, these ML algorithms have not been used for RAT selection in multiple RAN or base station scenarios before.

Analysis revealed that XGBoost showed the highest training accuracy, model performance accuracy, and also displayed its ability to predict future (unknown) dataset among large dataset without over-fitting problems. This is equally published and fully presented in chapter 5 accordingly.

Having investigated 5G NSA networks from the perspectives presented above, the researcher further extended the research to 5G SA, to address the third objective. Several efforts were also recorded in literature, and the following summarises, some of the relevant ones to our research area.

In [41], a survey on 5G RAN energy efficiency; massive MIMO, lean carrier design, sleep modes, and ML has been done. The authors surveyed base station power consumption models and metrics for the optimisation of energy efficiency. However, authors only laid emphasis on the role of spatio-temporal predictions and recommended an online optimisation via ML in power consumption minimisation task.

Also in [42], a data-driven framework for effective and quality aware Fog-RAN optimisation for 5G has been proposed. The authors leveraged on user mobility and traffic data in their study, to achieve infrastructure utilisation and handover quality improvement. Their proposal utilized a size-constrained community detection (SCUD) algorithm, to cluster remote radio heads (RRHs) into groups with frequent handover events. They formulated base band unit (BBU) allocation in each community fog server, as a set of partitioning problem, and used a column-reduced integer programming (CLIP) algorithm to find optimal BBU allocation schemes.

Furthermore in [43], authors investigated a double deep Q network (DDQN) based resource allocation (RA) framework, in a cloud radio access network (CRAN), to maximize the total energy efficiency, subject to the constraint on per RRHs transmission power selection and user data rates.

Here, authors formulated the EE problem as a Markov decision process (MDP) and further utilised deep reinforcement learning (DRL) method to achieve cumulative EE rewards. Simulation results were used to authenticate the double DQN based resource allocation method that saved over 22% power performance and improves performance of EE by 20%. However, authors did not consider pathloss in their optimisation and in deep Q-Learning, the Q-function can have many local optimal solutions, aside the targeted optimal global solution, which makes it difficult for the neural network to converge to the correct Q-function.

In another research publication in [44], a system model for joint user clustering and multi-dimensional resource allocation algorithm, to address the problem of co-channel interference in Multiple Input Multiple Output-Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (MIMO-NOMA), 5G communication network has been proposed. The algorithm which uses user location information and channel state information (CSI), has two optimisation problems, one targeting the effective capacity of users in the downlink multi-cell MIMO-NOMA network. While the second contains binary variables and continuous variables, which includes nonlinear constraints, that lead to a mixed integer nonlinear programming problem (MINLP). Authors only proposed iterative algorithm of graph theory, and optimisation theory based on Lagrangian dual problem solution to solve the optimisation problems. However, Lagrangian dual algorithm requires a huge computation complexity.

In addition in [45], an optimisation strategy and case analysis of 5G NSA wireless network in Xining City, China has been published. Where statistical analysis of main indicators; (weak coverage, handover coverage, overlapping coverage) of network were considered, and its optimisation was implemented by mere mechanical adjustment of azimuth angle of the antenna. Which in turn adjusted the power of the reference signal, for improvement in network resources utilisation and network performance. The authors did not utilise the current ML-based optimisation technique.

Likewise in [46], an optimisation of 5G NR network based on performance of 4G LTE network at Universitas Brawijaya Malang, Indonesia, has been carried out, where authors deployed drive tests to determine the site location mapping (gNB) and 5G NR network coverage of the university.

Their result according to publication is for future 5G NR network planning, which was further mapped into Atoll planning tool, hence optimisation exercise is more of engineering (network planning) type, that utilised 4G LTE network parameters.

Furthermore in [47], optimisation of network performance in 5G systems with downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) decoupling using MATLAB simulation has been done. Authors proposed a new uplink association method based on pathloss, while the downlink association still considers DL received power (RP), unlike UL/DL convention. Their research which is not also ML-based, called for further studies on optimisation techniques of decoupled network access for the 5G network in their conclusion.

In another publication, a synergistic optimisation of 5G networks that integrates genetic algorithms and particle swarm optimisation techniques has been proposed in [48]. Authors used their technique to address energy efficiency, traffic management, and channel allocation problems in a simulated system that involves 1000 users, 100 base stations, with 200 generations and a population size of 200 for both genetic algorithm (GA) and PSO. Although authors deployed known population optimisation algorithm tools, but GA-natural evolution based and PSO-social behavior based, are both metaheuristic algorithms, that apply stochastic operators in trying to find optimal results. GA usually converges towards a local optimum or even arbitrary points rather than the global optimum, while PSO easily falls into local optimum in high-dimensional space and has a low convergence rate in the iterative process.

In [49], authors proposed a deep reinforcement learning solution based on a Deep Q-Network (DQN) model, to ascertain the amount of traffic of a device delivered through each base station, making the decision as a function of the current traffic and radio conditions in an optimisation problem. Authors deployed a simulated square area of 500 m \times 500 m, composed of four 5G NR and two macro LTE base stations. Where they bench marked exhaustive search (optimal), and signal to interference noise (SINR) based cell association strategies to their DQN model results. They asserted their solution outperformed a reference scheme based on SINR with differences of up to 50% in terms of reward, and up to 166% in terms of throughput for certain situations.

However, DQN is known with convergence issue, time consuming and struggle to learn in environments with sparse rewards. Also in [50], a reinforcement learning (RL) approach for dynamic resource optimisation in 5G RAN Slicing has been presented, to find solution to an optimisation problem over a time horizon.

Authors considered communication (frequency-time blocks and transmit powers), plus computational resources (CPU usage) for downlink communications from the gNodeB to UEs. Authors used Q-learning to allocate resources to network slices randomly, but in Q-learning however, Q-function is typically nonlinear and can have many local minima.

Moreover in [51], a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) based cell association scheme for bandwidth management in 5G Fog-RAN has also been proposed. Where authors selected only date, system time, and cell-IDs of associated cell, from a public data containing date, system time (hour, minute, seconds), signal strength, and cell-ID for their model training activities. It is observed they neglected signal strength, and pathloss values are also not considered in their optimisation. They also used 180kHz bandwidth of an Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA); LTE based cellular system, unlike this study that utilises both 4G LTE and 5G networks of various bandwidth availability.

Similarly in [52], the problem of energy efficiency maximisation, through user association and beamforming in Fog-RAN, has been investigated. The optimisation problem was solved using Augmented Lagrangian (AL) method and a Heuristic low-complexity technique. To solve the user association and Fog Access Points (F-AP) activation in a centralized manner, and secondly used to solve for beamforming in a distributed manner respectively. Simulation results showed that the proposed Heuristic method achieved an increase in performance level as compared to the AL-based method. Although, Heuristic methods are known for good approximation given certain patterns, which is beneficial in certain practical scenarios, however, their optimal solution sometimes is not guaranteed. Hence, the need for an ML based method to validate their decision or vice versa. Heuristic method was therefore adopted, as basis of comparison to the proposed optimiser.

Therefore, following aforementioned existing literature, as main contribution of this study, this will be the first time pathloss will be considered as a major constraint, and also Gurobi (MILP) solver will be used for user association or RAT selection, and optimisation of data rate of users in literature. This has been submitted for publication and presented in chapter 6 of this thesis.

Table 2.5: Literature Review

Ref	Open problems	Research Focus	Metrics	Network	Solution	Gap
[41]	Optimisation of energy efficiency	Survey on 5G RAN	Energy efficiency; massive MIMO, lean carrier design, sleep modes, and machine learning	5G	Online optimisation via ML	Pathloss, Resource allocation
[42]	Handover quality improvement	Quality aware Fog-RAN optimisation	User mobility, Traffic data	5G	SCUD algorithm	ML, Pathloss, Resource allocation
[43]	Energy Efficiency	Resource allocation	RRHs transmission power, User data rates.	CRAN	Double deep Q network (DDQN), MDP, DRL	Pathloss
[44]	Co-channel interference	Resource allocation	User location, Channel state information (CSI)	5G MIMO-NOMA	Graph theory, Lagrangian dual algorithm	ML, Pathloss
[45]	Optimisation strategy	Network resources utilisation	Weak coverage, Handover coverage, Overlapping coverage	5G NSA	Mechanical adjustment	ML, Pathloss
[46]	5G NR network planning	Optimisation of 5G NR	Site location, Network coverage	4G	Engineering optimisation	ML, Pathloss, Resource allocation
[47]	Optimisation of network performance	Downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) decoupling	Pathloss, DL received power (RP)	5G	MATLAB Simulation	ML, Resource allocation
[48]	Channel allocation	Energy efficiency, Traffic management	Energy consumption and traffic load	5G	GA and Particle swarm optimisation (PSO)	ML, Pathloss, Resource allocation
[49]	Device traffic through each base station	Multi-connectivity optimization	Current traffic and radio conditions	5G NR and LTE base stations	Deep Q-Network (DQN) model	Pathloss, Resource allocation
[50]	Optimisation problem over a time horizon	Resource optimisation	Frequency-time blocks, Transmit power	5G RAN	Reinforcement learning (RL)	Pathloss
[51]	Bandwidth management	Cell association scheme	Date, System time, and cell-ID	LTE (OFDMA)	Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)	5G, Pathloss
[52]	Energy efficiency maximisation	User association and beamforming	Outdated channel metric	Fog-RAN	Augmented Lagrangian (AL), Heuristic	ML, Pathloss, Resource allocation
[Proposed]	RAT selection, Data (Resource) allocation	RAT selection, Data Rate Optimisation	Bandwidth, Number of users on base stations, Location of users and Pathloss	5G NR, 4G LTE	MILP (Gurobi) solver, Heuristic	-

2.6 Research Challenges in 5G Radio Access Technology

The term RAT, technically is the fundamental physical connection technique for a radio communication network. Hence, 5G RAT has to do with the underlying physical connection method with the NG-RAN of 5G system. In simple terms, it indicates the type of cellular network access technology deployed by a (MNO). For instance, 3G or 4G LTE or 5G New Radio (5G NR). Each representing a single RAT and a combination referred to as Multi-RAT.

Practically, the RAT is viewed independently as a separate system in terms of radio access, which can connect a mobile device with Multi-RAT feature through RAT selection to 4G LTE and 5G networks interchangeably. That is, users can be handed over from one RAT to another. In principle RAT selection basically requires three main factors; traffic pattern information of the UE, network coverage level information and cell loading consideration of each RAT [53]. These factors guided choice of parameters in our studies. At the moment, existing 5G deployments are based on NSA architecture, which still require support of 4G LTE infrastructure. Whereas, 5G SA uses only one RAT to connect to the 5G core network, since the 5G NR radio cells are used for both control plane and user plane. Hence, the 5G SA architecture will no longer depend on 4G infrastructure eventually, but there will be inter-generation handover between 4G and 5G [12] for service continuity, i.e., there will be 4G SA and 5G SA in Multi-RAT. Therefore, RAT selection becomes imperative.

2.6.1 Problem Statements

Based on previous literature review, and overview of 5G technology, where the need for RAT selection in 5G networks has been established, then the need to highlight research challenges, which are summarised as problem statements in this section.

Network of Choice: Several RAT selection approaches have been used in literature, where authors considered different networks of mobile generation, [25–28, 31, 33]. However, from observation all these authors only considered single network 4G LTE/WiFi or 5G/WiFi network for their researches.

Non utilized 4G/5G networks in their investigation. Hence, the uniqueness of this research that utilises 5G NR and underlying 4G LTE networks for apposite RAT selection.

Tools for Implementation: Several studies have implemented RAT selection using known methods like Matching Game Theory [26, 54], Probabilistic User Association approach [25, 55], and Q-Reinforcement Learning [56] respectively. However, RAT selection is a form of classification problem. Hence, our adoption of ML classification algorithms for RAT selection. Using DT [28], as a benchmark to other ML classification algorithms, that have not been used in literature for RAT selection.

Scenarios and Criteria used: Several studies like [25–28, 31, 33], have only considered 4G signal measurement parameters like SINR, RSRP and RSRQ during investigation, even when they claim their study is on 5G. Hence, there is lack of public 5G data as a form of contribution to knowledge. This study however, has addressed that, by providing 5G network related parameters: SS-RSRP, SS-RSRQ, SS-SINR, in addition to underlying 4G (LTE) network parameters: SINR, RSRP and RSRQ. Furthermore, researcher has proposed the utilization of users' Geo-location (longitude or latitude), bandwidth requirement of users, plus RSSI from base station as basic parameters, to predict or select suitable RAT, using ML technique in 5G NSA. Subsequently, researcher also proposed a novel optimiser using unique constraints for RAT selection and data rate allocation, applicable in 5G SA and beyond scenarios.

2.7 Proposed Solution

2.7.1 Machine Learning

In simple terms, machine learning is an act of teaching a computer model how to make prediction, and draw conclusion from data. In broad term, machine learning is the application of artificial intelligence (AI), that utilises statistical methods to build a mathematical model, train the model with sample data known as training data; which provides systems the ability to automatically learn from historic data [57], and improve from experience. In order to make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed for the task.

Hence, in mathematical expression, it can be stated as mapping input variables x to an output variable y , and can be expressed as stated in equation 2.1:

$$y = f(x) \quad (2.1)$$

2.7.2 Categories of Machine Learning

There are three main categories of machine learning:

- **Supervised learning:** This algorithm behaves like having a tutor or supervisor who knows the routine, and already has an idea of the end result. In other words, supervised learning algorithm builds a mathematical model from labelled input training dataset, with anticipated labelled output. Meaning, supervised learning maps labelled inputs (x) to outputs (y), as formalised in equation 2.1, making it ideal for classification tasks like RAT selection.

It can be divided into (i) Classification algorithm; which is used for a categorized labelled output e.g., 4G or 5G. (ii) Regression algorithm; which can be used to predict quantitative values like distance, longitude, latitude or signal strength. Examples of supervised learning algorithms are (DT) as used for RAT selection in [28]. Other examples are Extra Tree (XTREE), Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting (GB), eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Support Vector Machine (SVM) as utilised for RAT selection in chapter 4 and chapter 5 respectively.

- **Unsupervised learning:** Unlike supervised algorithm, this algorithm is based on data with common features or relationship and the output label is unknown. In other words, its algorithm builds a mathematical model from a labelled input training dataset only, and no anticipated output. It can be divided into (i) Clustering algorithm; which is used to find common structure in the data. Like grouping or clustering of data points based on relationship. For example, grouping mobile subscribers based on their application purchase or usage. (ii) Association algorithm; which entails discovering the rules that describe large portion of data.

For instance finding users that buy or deploy both application A and B. Alternatively, finding users that subscribe to MNO_1 or MNO_2. Examples of unsupervised learning algorithms are Hierarchical clustering, K-means, Anomaly detection, and Neural Network. Deep Neural Network is used in chapter 5.

- Reinforcement learning (RL): This algorithm adopts trial and error approach to make inference. It involves using successive trials as a form of reinforcement to produce output [58]. Typically, it has an agent that studies an environment; learns how to behave in the environment, by performing actions and evaluating the results through repeated efforts, for appropriate decision or prediction.

Examples of RL include: Markov Decision Process (MDP) and Q-learning method. Samples of programming languages used for ML include Python, Java, R and Tensor flow. For this research, Jupyter Notebook editor of the popular Anaconda-Python programming environment, was utilized as the ML tool.

2.8 Research Methodology

Figure 2.7: Pictorial view of pedestrian user and 5G NSA base station.

2.8.1 The First Objective

To achieve the first objective, this research utilised a network setup as depicted in Fig. 2.7. The figure presents the pictorial view of the 5G NSA base station, accessed by a mobile pedestrian user, for Multi-RAT selection.

The network setup basically comprises of the UE held by a pedestrian, 5G NSA base station, that further connects to the core network. Full implementation is presented in chapter 3 of this thesis.

2.8.2 The Second Objective

Figure 2.8: Pictorial view of a travelling mobile network user and 5G NSA base stations.

In order to accomplish the second objective, this research used a travelling mobile user in a public bus, whose overview is as depicted in Fig. 2.8. The mobile user transversed multiple 5G NSA base stations in the process. This is in furtherance to the first objective, where researcher utilised a pedestrian user, and single base station, for appropriate Multi-RAT selection. Full implementation is presented in chapter 4 of this thesis.

2.8.3 The Third Objective

Furthermore, in order to accomplish the third objective, with respect to 5G SA network, as depicted in Fig. 2.9, this research implemented RAT selection with data rate allocation to multiple users, via a novel ML integrable optimiser. Full implementation is presented in chapter 5 of this thesis..

Figure 2.9: Pictorial view of multi-users for RAT selection in 5G/4G SA networks.

2.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter presents an overview of the research work, and its literature review. However, the following chapter discusses analysis of Multi-RAT selection in 5G NSA network, using various tree-based machine learning classification algorithms.

Chapter 3

Machine Learning Analysis of Multi-RAT Selection in 5G NSA Network

3.1 Introduction

The exponential growth of traffic across the mobile networks called for exploitation of new spectrum bands of 5G networks; whose deployment still rely on support from underlying 4G LTE networks, in both 5G SA and NSA architectures. This scenario poses challenges on the choice of RAT selection between 4G LTE and 5G NR networks, to these ever increasing mobile users, with respect to their geographical location, mobility, and network coverage. Hence, this chapter investigates joint user requirements and network constraints for appropriate RAT selection between 4G LTE and 5G NR, by recording live radio measurements, over a distance of 300 meters between a pedestrian user and 5G NSA base station. The problem is formulated as a classification process, and implemented with classification ML algorithms: DT, XTREE, RF, GB, and XGBoost, to select an appropriate RAT. Evaluation of results with standard classification metrics, shows measure of accuracy of algorithms: DT at 91.82%, RF at 87.64%, XTREE at 86.75%, GB at 91.86%, and XGBoost at 93.86%, where XGBoost records highest performance value. Therefore, proposed as ML model for RAT selection to achieve efficient resource allocation.

3.2 Chapter Background

The tremendous traffic increase in mobile networks, especially with current usage of smart phones and wireless devices such as tablets and laptops operating between 700MHz and 6GHz, with channel bandwidth of 5 to 100MHz [9], resulted into spectrum crunch, in order to meet up with this challenge; the 5G networks are explored coupled with support from underlying network 4G LTE, which has been tested and trusted, in both 5G SA and NSA architectures.

Practically, NSA combines multiple RATs by inter-wiring with existing 4G LTE network [12]; i.e., the 5G NR radio cells are combined with 4G LTE radio cells, using dual connectivity (DC) to provide radio access before connecting to the core network (CN); which can either be EPC or 5G core (5GC), to offer higher mobile broadband speeds, through its eMBB features.

Presently, existing 5G deployments are based on NSA architecture which still require support of 4G LTE infrastructure. However, 5G SA which is a pure end-to-end 5G network uses only one RAT to connect to the 5GC core network, that is, the 5G NR radio cells are used for both control and user planes.

Although, 5G SA architecture will no longer depends on 4G infrastructure, but there will still be inter-generation handover between 4G and 5G [12] for service continuity, i.e., there will be 4G SA and 5G SA in Multi-RAT. This will stimulate seamless connectivity of users for uRLLC experience, network slicing capabilities and mMTC applications, for better support to internet of things (IoT) devices.

Therefore, in the present and nearest future of mobile networks deployment, 5G will co-exist with different technologies like 4G in a Multi-RAT environment [13, 14]. This motivates the investigation of RAT selection between 4G LTE and 5G NR in Multi-RAT environments.

Fundamentally, the term RAT simply connotes the type of cellular network access technology deployed by a mobile network operator (MNO); e.g. 3G or 4G LTE or 5G. Each representing a single RAT and a combination referred to as Multi-RAT.

Operationally, each RAT is viewed independently as a separate system in terms of radio access; which can connect a mobile device with Multi-RAT feature through RAT selection to 4G LTE and 5G networks interchangeably; where users can be handed over from one RAT to another.

In principle, RAT selection basically requires three main factors; traffic pattern information of a mobile device, network coverage level information, and cell loading consideration of each RAT [53], which guided the choice of parameters; geographical location of a pedestrian user recorded as latitude and longitude as well as received signal strength indicator (RSSI) from a 5G NSA network. Meanwhile, with the quantum increment in the number of mobile user devices estimated at 5.33 Billion [59] today; which is about 2/3 of the total world population of 7.95 Billion [60], pushing traffic through the existing RATs of 5G NR and underlying 4G LTE. Then, the need for an intelligent method that can handle and manage voluminous data effectively, has the ability to reduce computational complexities and prediction time, Hence, the adoption of machine learning algorithm with aforementioned features for RAT implementation in this study.

Consequently, as part of this study's consideration, emphases are placed on the speed of processing of machine learning algorithms implored, their ability to predict (select) accurately, and mitigate overfitting of data; due to subscribers upsurge, that might arise during machine learning process, synonymous with previous machine learning methods used for RAT selection in literature. Therefore, the need for this study to achieve a fast machine learning RAT selection scheme, that can guarantee efficient resource allocation between 4G LTE and 5G NR RATs, with consideration to user's geographical location, mobility and network coverage, that can deliver required network throughput effectively for user's satisfaction.

3.2.1 Study Methodology

This chapter utilizes live signal measurements of 5G NSA network; as shown in the network topology in Fig. 3.1. The 5G NSA architecture allows the 5G NR to utilize 5G for radio to UE communication (down-link), while relying on 4G LTE for the UE to radio-head (up-link) communication, before connecting to the 5GC core.

Figure 3.1: The 5G non-stand alone network topology.

It operates at 2.6/2.5GHz up-link and down-link frequencies, respectively. The key contributions of this study include:

- Live signal measurements of 5G NR, and underlying 4G LTE networks, in contrast to simulated ones from a single network 5G or 4G/WiFi or 5G/WiFi in previous studies, are used for RAT selection in this chapter.
- Geo-location (longitude, latitude) of UE, and RSSI from base station are used as basic parameters, different from previously used ones in literature.
- The RAT selection is implemented with DT as benchmark, and further carried out with other standard tree-based classification machine learning algorithms: Extra Tree (XTREE), Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting (GB), and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), whose algorithm is presented in section 3.6.

- Execution time of each algorithm is evaluated, to obtain their respective speed of computation, were further calculated, as presented in section 3.7.2.
- Evaluation of each model performance using the following standard classification evaluation metrics [61] : accuracy, precision, recall, and F-score, with a comprehensive comparative analysis of algorithms performance evaluation, as presented in section 3.7.2.
- In addition, validation of these models are carried out with cross-validation score function, to determine their proficiency on future datasets as presented in section 3.7.3. Hence, based on past literature, this will be the first time RAT selection research work will be investigated using this approach.

3.3 System Model and Problem Formulation

Considering the Multi-RAT system model as depicted in Fig. 3.1, where users can be handed over from one RAT to another based on network coverage, their location and mobility, which guided the input parameters; RSSI on network side and geographical location of a pedestrian on user's side respectively, to select an output variable RAT.

Based on parameters above, a user selects the most appropriate RAT; 4G(RAT-A) or 5G NR(RAT-B) to perform connection action, where the set of all possible actions (A) in choosing either RAT-A or RAT-B is represented as: $\{a_0, a_1\}$, where a_0 denotes the action of dropping a RAT and a_1 indicates choosing the alternative RAT for connection.

Let the network coverage level (C) of each RAT be considered as $\{c_1; c_2\}$, where it is assumed that network transmission is reliable. Also, parameter (d) which represents distance in meters; signifies location of a user from the base station. Hence, the connection status (S) is defined by the following vector of features: $\{c_1; c_2, d\}$, the vector (S) will be utilized to determine the most appropriate connection action. $A \in a_0, a_1$ which represents the event of dropping a RAT or using the alternative appropriate RAT. Clearly, this is a classification problem, that require a framework that can manage voluminous data effectively; hence, the adoption of ML classification algorithms for implementation.

3.4 Machine Learning for Multi-RAT

Since RAT selection is categorised as classification problem, hence in this chapter, measured field data via Anaconda-Python ML tool, are fed into the following supervised classification algorithms, whose models can be found in [62]:

- Decision Tree (DT); is a tree shaped ML algorithm which can be used to determine the course of action, each branch of tree represents possible decision, occurrence, or solution; hence DT can be used for classification purpose, for instance choosing between 4G and 5G NR.
- Random Forest (RF); is a ML algorithm that builds decision trees on different samples independently and takes their majority vote for classification; for instance 4G / 5G NR or average when used for regression.
- Extra Trees (XTREE); is an ensemble ML algorithm that adds up the predictions from many decision trees. It is related to random forest algorithm, hence, it can be used for regression and also classification (e.g, choosing between 4G and 5G NR).
- Gradient Boosting (GB); is also a set of decision trees that builds one tree at a time, and tries to accurately predict a target variable (e.g RAT) by combining the estimates of a set of simpler or weaker models, this accounts for its better performance in relation to previous algorithms.
- Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost); is an ensemble, gradient-boosted decision tree (GBDT) ML algorithm, a scalable end-to-end tree boosting system that has many hyperparameters for fine-tuning, and its the foremost ML algorithm used for ranking, regression, and classification problems. Hence, its adoption as proposed ML tool, based on its outstanding performance.

3.5 Data Collection Method

The focus of this chapter is to utilize live 5G/4G data, and classification supervised ML algorithm to develop a model to select the appropriate RAT for pedestrian mobile networks users, for efficient resource allocation. In order to accomplish this objective, live signal measurements of 5G NSA network were recorded in Edinburgh, Scotland; an area whose propagation environment can be classified as dense-Urban [7]. It was specifically chosen as an investigation area due to the availability of 5G network footprint, of the selected UK mobile service provider in this area. Data were carefully collected using walk tests technique [63], between December 2021 and May 2022 in the area of investigation as shown in Fig. 3.2 [64]. The main tools utilised include Samsung Galaxy A52s; a 5G-enabled Multi-RAT mobile phone and HP-EliteBook laptop as depicted in Fig. 3.1. The phone is equipped with Cellular-Z; an application software through which network information such as serving cell, signal strength, neighbouring cells information, Geographical location (latitude, longitude) and many more can be obtained. Field UE measurements were taken at 1.5 meter space over a distance of 300 meters, between the mobile phone and the base station by a pedestrian user. Log files from the application were then exported into Microsoft Excel, saved in CSV format and analyzed with a ML tool; anaconda-Python programming language based, to select either 4G LTE or 5G RAT.

3.5.1 Measured Parameters in 4G LTE

In 4G LTE, signal measurements are employed to perform base station selection, reselection and handover. Its measured parameters are associated with base station or cell reference signal (CRS), and hence, classified as RSRP, RSRQ and RSSI [65] as highlighted below:

- Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP): RSRP typically ranges from -140 dBm to -44 dBm.
- Reference Signal Received Quality (RSRQ): Its reporting range is from -19.5 dB to -3 dB.

Figure 3.2: Investigated area: Easter road Edinburgh, Scotland.

- Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI): RSSI is a measure of power and can be mathematically expressed as it relates with RSRP and RSRQ in equation 3.1 thus:

$$RSSI = N * \left(\frac{RSRP}{RSRQ} \right) \quad (3.1)$$

where N is the number of resource blocks (RBs) per channel bandwidth.

3.5.2 Measured Parameters in 5G

In 5G networks, synchronization signal (SS) and channel state information (CSI), instead of CRS are used. Hence, due to its own peculiar configuration, 3GPP [66] defines new parameters for 5G signal measurements as stated below:

- Synchronization Signal Reference Signal Received Power (SS-RSRP).

- Secondary Synchronization Signal Reference Signal Received Quality (SS-RSRQ).
- RSSI can also be mathematically expressed as equation 3.2 thus:

$$RSSI = N * \left(\frac{SS - RSRP}{SS - RSRQ} \right), \quad (3.2)$$

where N is the number of resource blocks in the $RSSI(NR)$ measurement bandwidth.

3.6 Multi-RAT Implementation

The following parameters: latitude, longitude, and RSSI (which is common to 5G NR and 4G LTE in 5G NSA architecture depending on the RAT a user is connected), among other radio parameters were recorded via the UE and saved in form of log file. The log file was later exported into Microsoft Excel, and saved as CSV (comma-separated values) file format, which allows data to be saved in a table structured format (200 rows X 9 columns), suitable for ML tool analysis. The full data is available in [67]). As shown in the RAT selection Algorithm 1, the pseudo-code can be expressed in nested if-else sequence, to obtain either 4G or 5G as output; defined as RAT, after checking input data parameters conditions. The algorithm begins with a start timer, where the computational speed of algorithm is initialized. The CSV file named (celldata.csv) is imported (load) into Jupyter notebook; a ML environment programming language. After this, input data (latitude, longitude, RSSI) and output data (RAT), which can be either 4G or 5G, are defined as X and y parameters respectively, which were further divided into training and testing datasets; X -train, y -train, and X -test, y -test respectively. An instance of a model of DT, or XTREE, or RF, or GB, or XGBoost is (called) initiated, to predict (select) a suitable RAT. The Geo-location (latitude, longitude) and RSSI, are used as input data (features); X_{ijk} , to obtain the appropriate RAT; $y_i = 4G$ or $5G$ as labelled output. Thereafter, the model is then trained with the input and output training datasets; X -train and y -train to predict y -test i.e., to select either 4G or 5G RAT network. Furthermore, the performance evaluation metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F-Score) of classification algorithms and cross-validation score, are used to evaluate and validate the model performance respectively.

Algorithm 1 Algorithm for Machine Learning based RAT Selection

```

Require: data
Ensure: RAT
begin
start timer
Load data (celldata.csv) in CSV file format
Define input (X) and output (y) training and test datasets
Call instance of a model: (DT) / (XTREE) / (RF) / (GB), or (XGBoost)
Split data: X-train, X-test, y-train, y-test
 $X_{ijk} = \langle \text{latitude, longitude, RSSI} \rangle$ 
 $y_i = \langle 4G \text{ or } 5G \rangle$ 
Train the model: X-train, y-train
Define evaluation metrics
if latitude =  $X_i$ , longitude =  $X_j$  and RSSI =  $X_k$  then
     $y_i = 4G$ 
else
    if latitude =  $X'_i$ , longitude =  $X'_j$  and RSSI =  $X'_k$  then
         $y_i = 5G$ 
    end if
end if
Test the model: X-test
Predict (select) RAT: y-test
Score model
stop timer
Print results
end

```

These are defined and executed at the score model. After the performance evaluation above, the timer stops, and the results follow; RAT selected, computation speed, and performance evaluation metrics (printed) displayed. The full code of implementation is available in [68].

3.7 Performance Evaluation

To achieve the first objective of research in this chapter, performance evaluation is based on; computational speed of each ML algorithm, classification metrics evaluation results, and cross-validation scores. Iteration was carried out ten times for each algorithm, and the average of the collated values were calculated, to obtain performance evaluation results as highlighted in the following sections.

Table 3.1: Computational Speed

Algorithm	Parameters	
	Execution-Time	Execution-Rate
DT	0.286	Medium
RF	1.155	Lowest
XTree	0.956	Low
GB	0.231	Fast
XGBoost	0.204	Fastest

3.7.1 Speed of Algorithms

The execution time; which is the inverse of the speed of algorithm was evaluated, to obtain the computational speed of each algorithm implored, using the following equation in equation 3.3:

$$execution_time = stop_time - start_time \quad (3.3)$$

Since speed is inversely proportional to time, hence, the algorithm with the smallest execution time is rated as having the fastest computational speed. From observation, it is revealed that; DT, RF, XTREE, GB and XGBoost have the following execution time: 0.286, 1.155, 0.956, 0.231, 0.204 respectively, as captured in Fig. 3.3.

Therefore, they are rated accordingly from highest computational speed, to the lowest as follows: XGBoost-fastest, GB-fast, DT-medium, XTREE-low, and the least; RF algorithm rated lowest as presented in Table 3.1.

3.7.2 Evaluation Results Analysis

Evaluation of algorithms was carried out with 80% of collated data as training dataset, while the remaining 20% were used as testing dataset. The following standard classification evaluation metrics whose formulae have already been stated in [61] were used. Generally, the value of each metric is between 0 and 1, where the higher value shows better result.

- **Accuracy:** is the ratio of correct predictions (true positive results, true negative results) to the total number of instances evaluated. It produces what proportion of prediction does the model get right. Observed results as tabulated in Table 3.2, showed accuracy of algorithms as follows: DT 0.918, RF 0.876, XTREE 0.867, GB 0.918 and XGBoost 0.938. Fig. 3.4 presents the accuracy of algorithms, where x-axis represents the algorithms, and y-axis represents the corresponding metric rate of each algorithm.
- **Precision:** can be defined as the number of true positive results divided by the number of all positive results, including results not correctly identified. It reflects the more relevant results than the irrelevant ones. As observed in Table 3.2, precision of algorithms are: DT 0.899, RF 0.891, XTREE 0.869, GB 0.902, and XGBoost 0.910. Fig. 3.5 features the precision of algorithms, where x-axis represents the algorithms, and y-axis represents the corresponding metric rate of each algorithm.
- **Recall:** is defined as the number of true positive results divided by the number of all sample datasets, that should have been recognised as positive. It connotes that an algorithm returns most of the relevant results, whether or not irrelevant ones are also returned. Recall results obtained as tabulated in Table 3.2, recorded DT 0.911, RF 0.884 and XTREE 0.872, GB 0.901 and XGBoost 0.945. Fig. 3.6 showcases the recall of algorithms, where x-axis represents the algorithms, and y-axis represents the corresponding metric rate of each algorithm.
- **F-Score:** is an overall metric (harmonic mean) that essentially combines precision and recall as a measure of model's performance. Evaluation based on F-score results showed DT 0.914, RF 0.885, XTREE 0.862, GB 0.894 and XGBoost 0.911 as tabulated in Table 3.2. Fig. 3.7 presents the F-Score of algorithms, where x-axis represents the algorithms, while the y-axis represents the corresponding metric rate of each algorithm.

These are further compared pictorially in Fig. 3.8. Observation showed XGBoost algorithm performance having best evaluation metrics results, among all algorithms investigated. Hence, XGBoost adopted and proposed for RAT selection.

Figure 3.3: Algorithms computational speed.

Table 3.2: Classification Evaluation Metrics

Algorithm	Metrics			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F-Score
DT	0.918	0.899	0.911	0.914
RF	0.876	0.891	0.884	0.885
XTREE	0.867	0.869	0.872	0.862
GB	0.918	0.902	0.901	0.894
XGBoost	0.938	0.910	0.945	0.911

Figure 3.4: Accuracy evaluation metric of Algorithms.

Figure 3.5: Precision evaluation metric of Algorithms.

Figure 3.6: Recall evaluation metric of Algorithms.

3.7.3 Validation of Algorithms

Although evaluation metrics measure the ratio of the number of correct predictions (RAT selection) to the total number of input samples, which have been shown in accuracy, precision, recall and F-score metrics above. However, it is also established in [69] that a good model is not the one that gives accurate predictions on known training dataset alone, but a model that also gives good predictions on new (future) dataset, avoids over-fitting and under-fitting issues, therefore, models validation was carried out with cross-validation score metric.

Figure 3.7: F-Score evaluation metric of Algorithms.

Figure 3.8: Comparison of Metrics Evaluation of Algorithms.

Table 3.3: Cross Validation Metric

Algorithm	Cross-Val
DT	0.909
RF	0.912
XTree	0.918
GB	0.918
XGBoost	0.929

Figure 3.9: Cross validation score of Algorithms.

Basically, cross-validation is used in ML to assess the proficiency of a ML model on unseen future data. This is done by using a limited sample of training dataset to evaluate the model performance in totality, when used to make predictions on dataset not used during its training. The cross-validation score values are as presented in Table 3.3, and findings as pictured in Fig. 4.11. Where it is observed that DT, RF, XTREE, GB and XGBoost have the following cross-validation scores: 0.909, 0.912, 0.918, 0.918, 0.929 respectively. Similarly, the proposed model (XGBoost) again shows highest 92.9% validation score.

3.8 Conclusion

In this chapter, ML algorithms for effective RAT selection and efficient resource allocation in 5G NSA network were presented. Geo-location (latitude and longitude) of the user, as well as the received signal strength indicator (RSSI) from a live 5G NSA base station, common to both 4G LTE and 5G NR RATs were used as basic parameters. Data collated were divided into training and testing datasets. The training datasets (input) were used to train models of supervised learning classification algorithms: DT, XTREE, RF, GB, and XGBoost. These trained models were further tested with input test datasets to predict/select the appropriate RAT (4G/5G) as labelled output.

Evaluation of results showed a measure of accuracy of the proposed model; XGBoost at optimal level of 93.86%, which was further cross validated at 92.9%, when compared with other algorithms for its effectiveness on future data, and mitigation ability on over-fitting and under-fitting issues. Hence, recommended for planning and optimization purposes in similar urban/dense-urban environment, to assist in maintaining the rapidly increasing demand of network connections and devices.

3.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter addresses the first objective, with the adoption of ML tools for the analysis of Multi-RAT selection in 5G NSA network, by a pedestrian user. The second objective of this research, is thus investigated further, using other parameters like user's mobility, bandwidth requirement, and data rate of a travelling user in a public bus, for appropriate RAT selection, in the following chapter.

Chapter 4

Machine Learning Approach for Travelling Users in 5G NSA Networks

4.1 Introduction

The rapid increment of mobile devices usage, and the corresponding huge data volume generated afterwards, necessitated the utilisation of the 5G network spectrum. This is deployed today in terrestrial communication in a NSA architectural mode; where 5G networks are supported by 4G LTE networks. Hence, the current 5G implementation with the gargantuan number of mobile subscribers, poses challenges to the choice of network Radio Access Technology (RAT) selection between 4G and 5G networks, among available multiple base-stations to mobile (traveling) users, with respect to their location, bandwidth requirement, and mobility style. Hence, to address the second objective as presented in the scenario above, live signal measurements of 4G and 5G networks by a traveling user, that transversed multiple 5G NSA base stations, were recorded. RAT selection implementations were carried out with SVM, DNN, and XGBoost algorithms to select an appropriate RAT between 4G and 5G RATs, for effective resource allocation for traveling users' requirements. Evaluation of results with standard classification metrics shows XGBoost with overall outstanding accuracy performance at 99.64%.

4.2 Chapter Background

The current generation of mobile communication; 5G networks, which is currently deployed as NSA architecture in Multi-RAT fashion, introduced a paradigm shift towards a user-centric technology framework. This requires an efficient and effective RAT selection scheme, which supports three essential use cases: eMBB, mMTC, and URLLC, with stipulated ultra-high data rate, ultra-low latency, and abundant bandwidth. This scheme needs to be responsive to users' demands, mobility, network requirements, and backhaul capabilities, which are imperative due to heavy traffic across the networks.

RAT is the underlying physical connection method for a radio communication network. It simply indicates the kind of cellular network access technology deployed by a mobile network operator (MNO) e.g., 3G or 4G LTE or 5G New Radio (5G NR), each representing a single RAT and a combination referred to as Multi-RAT. However, RAT selection fundamentally requires the following factors: traffic pattern information of a mobile device, network coverage level information, and cell loading consideration of each RAT [53], which informed the choice of parameters; the geographical location of a traveling user recorded as latitude and longitude, data rate experienced by the user, received signal strength indicator (RSSI) and bandwidth of each RAT, in multiple 5G NSA base stations scenario as depicted in Fig. 4.1.

In general, RAT technologies can be characterized based on deployment, coverage, performance, and security [70]. Hence, from the literature, RAT selection that supports multiple connectivity in 5G networks, can be grouped into four main types: i.) Cellular: which consists of 4G LTE and 5G NR, ii.) Wireless Fidelity (WiFi): which includes IEEE 802.11ac and IEEE 802.11p, iii.) Low-Power Wide-Area (LPWA): which comprises of Narrowband Internet of things (NB-IoT) and Long Range (LoRA), and iv.) Satellite communication at Low Earth Orbit (LEO). RAT selection can also be viewed as: a) User-centric or b) Network-centric RAT selection. Hence, the peculiarity of this study, that combines both network and user parameters in cellular 5G and 4G LTE networks.

Figure 4.1: Research (Multi-RAT) Topology.

Meanwhile, this study adopts the ML technique due to its ability to manage large data efficiently, and its capacity to minimize computational complexities (e.g., in voice or action recognition [71]) and prediction time. Hence, this chapter specifically addresses challenges faced by mobile users traveling in public buses, (since the use of a mobile phone while driving a car is prohibited), which has not been researched before in previous literature. These group of users account for a high percentage of mobile subscriptions in the UK; the country of chosen investigated areas. Fig. 4.2 shows smartphone users age groups in UK, between 2012-2022.

Therefore, the focus of this chapter, is to develop an intelligent predictive model using a combination of parameters: Geo-location (latitude and longitude), data rate experience of the mobile user traveling in a public bus, network coverage capacity in terms of RSSI, and available bandwidth, that will select an appropriate RAT (4G/5G) among multiple 5G NSA base stations, for efficient management of large number of subscribers in 5G and future networks to achieve effective resource allocation.

Figure 4.2: UK smartphone users by age in 2012-2022 [2].

4.2.1 Study Methodology

In this chapter, live signal measurements of multiple 5G NSA network base stations from a traveling user were utilized; the study topology is as depicted in Fig. 4.1, where the 5G NSA architecture allows the 5G NR to utilize 5G for radio to UE communication (down-link), while relying on 4G LTE for the UE to radio-head (up-link) communication, before connecting to the EPC; 5G NSA option 3 [12]. Hence, the key advancements in this chapter include:

- Implementation of RAT selection using live signal measurements of 5G NR, and underlying 4G LTE networks, from multiple base stations in contrast to simulated ones in previous studies.
- All measurements were geotagged with timestamps to correlate mobility patterns with network conditions.

- Usage of Geo-location (longitude, latitude), the data rate of UE, in addition to RSSI and bandwidth of base stations, as basic parameters, different from previously used ones in the literature.
- Implementation of RAT selection with XGBoost as a benchmark, to other classification ML algorithms that got their classification capability acknowledged by the computer vision community [40]. The algorithm of implementation is presented in section 4.6.
- A comparative analysis of these three highly rated predictors in machine learning; SVM, DNN, and XGBoost performance, in RAT selection application.
- Training accuracy computed, and further used to calculate the execution time of each algorithm considered, to obtain their respective speed of computation. As presented in sections 4.7.1 and 4.7.2 respectively.
- Evaluation of each model performance, using the following standard classification evaluation metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, and F-score, with their results analysis as presented in section 4.7.3.
- In addition, the cross-validation score function was used for validation purposes, to determine model proficiency on future datasets as presented in section 4.7.4.

This chapter is structured as follows: section 4.3 details the data collection methodology, section 4.4 presents the system model and problem formulation, section 4.5 elucidates field data measurement procedure, while section 4.6 describes the Multi-RAT implementation. Performance evaluation and validation are presented in section 4.7 and 4.8 respectively.

4.3 Data Collection Method

Live 5G/4G radio measurement data were carefully recorded, across a total of 47 (multiple) 5G NSA base stations, between Paisley (Sub-urban) and Glasgow (Urban) terrains, over a distance of 12.6 miles (20.28 km) [72].

Table 4.1: Data Collation Information

Item	Details
Duration	Sept. 2022 - Feb. 2023
Distance covered	12.6 miles (20.28 km)
Average speed of bus	35 miles/hr (56.33 km/h)
No of User(s)	1
No of 4G RATs	47
No of 5G RATs	47
Measuring Device	Samsung Galaxy A52s
ML platform	Anaconda-Python
ML Algorithms	SVM, DNN & XGBoost

Table 4.1 shows the key data collation information. Areas of investigation were chosen due to the availability of 5G and 4G footprints of the selected UK mobile service providers in these regions. Samsung Galaxy A52s 5G enabled phone, equipped with Cellular-z software application, was used by a traveling user in a public bus, moving at an average speed of 35 miles/hr (56.33 km/h) [73]. Through the cellular-application software, network information such as serving cell, signal strength, neighboring cells information, geographical location (latitude, longitude), cell type, frequency band of operation and other parameters can be recorded.

Hence, field UE measurements were taken at 50 meters apart, over a total distance of 12.6 miles (20.28 km), between High Street in Paisley as the starting point, and Buchanan bus station in Glasgow as the destination. Data were methodologically collected using the walk tests technique [74], between September 2022 and February 2023, in areas of investigation as shown in Fig. 4.3. The collected signal measurements in the form of log files from the application were then exported into Microsoft Excel for collation, saved in CSV format, and analyzed with a ML tool; anaconda-Python programming language, whose models were used to train the data from Excel.

Figure 4.3: Investigated area [starting point: High street Paisley, endpoint: Buchanan bus station Glasgow, distance: 12.6 miles.

Geo-location (latitude, longitude), data rate, RSSI, and bandwidth were set as objective functions (input parameters). The ML models were trained with the input parameters after good performance training stops, otherwise model is updated with new sets of parameters (iteration). The trained model with experience is now tested with fresh data to select either 4G LTE or 5G RAT.

4.4 System Model and Problem Formulation

Mobility depicts the movement of mobile users to their location, velocity, and direction over some time. These are captured as the geographical location of the traveling user (latitude and longitude), a public bus traveling at the average speed of 35 miles/hr (56.33 km/h) from Paisley High Street to Buchanan bus station in Glasgow, UK, covering a distance of 12.6 miles (20.28 km) at an estimated time of 33 mins per trip, as shown in Fig. 4.3. Hence, considering the Multi-RAT system model as depicted in Fig. 4.1, where traveling (mobile) user(s) can be sequentially handed over from one RAT to another, e.g., from 4G (RAT-A) to 5G NR (RAT-B) or vice versa, based on network coverage, their location and mobility, which guided the input parameters; geographical location a traveling user recorded as latitude and longitude, data rate at UE, received signal strength indicator (RSSI) from multiple 5G NSA base stations and bandwidth of each network to select an

output variable RAT. Let the number of traveling users transversing through the set of base station (BS) be denoted as $U = U_1, U_2, \dots, U_i$, while, the set of NSA base stations be denoted as $BS = B_1, B_2, \dots, B_j$, where each contains 4G (RAT-A) and 5G NR (RAT-B) respectively. Following the study field observation, a user can only associate with a single BS at a time. Hence, the association matrix between the base stations and travelling user U_i , in the public bus is denoted as $A = A_{11}, A_{12}, \dots, A_{ij}$, where the association variable between traveling user U_i and base station B_j , is expressed as A_{ij} , and it can be either 0 or 1. Then, to perform connection action, where the set of all possible association action (A), in choosing either RAT-A or RAT-B in all base stations, is represented as: $\{a_0^1, a_1^1\}, \{a_0^2, a_1^2\} \dots \{a_0^j, a_1^j\}$, where the number of base station = 1 to j .

Hence, $\{a_0^1, a_1^1\}$, denotes the action of dropping a RAT or choosing the alternative RAT for connection in base station B_1 . Similarly, $\{a_0^2, a_1^2\}$, denotes the action of dropping a RAT or choosing the other RAT for connection in base station B_2 , and so on. Let the network coverage level (C) of each RAT be considered as $\{c_1^j, c_2^j\}$, where it is assumed that network transmission is reliable. Meanwhile, parameter B_w also stands for available bandwidth, while V_b , represents the average speed of a traveling bus in miles per hour. Hence, the connection status (S) of the traveling user can be defined by the following vector of features: $\{c_1^j, c_2^j, V_b, B_w\}$.

Therefore, the vector (S) will be utilized to determine the most appropriate RAT connection (association) action: $A \in a_0^j, a_1^j$; which represents the event of dropping a RAT or using the alternative appropriate RAT in a base station. It is observed that the RAT selection problem formulation above is a classification type. Therefore, the following ML classification algorithms are adopted for implementation.

4.4.1 Machine Learning for Multi-RAT Selection

In broad terms, machine learning is the application of artificial intelligence (AI), that utilises statistical methods, to build a mathematical model, and train the model with sample data known as training data; thereby providing systems the ability to automatically learn from historical data [57], and improve from experience, to make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed for the task.

Mathematically, this can be viewed as mapping input variables x to an output variable y , and can be expressed as equation 4.1 thus:

$$y = f(x) \quad (4.1)$$

Machine learning is categorised as supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement learning. Supervised learning, can be further divided into classification and regression algorithms, while unsupervised machine learning can also be divided into clustering and association algorithms. The reinforcement learning also has MDP and Q learning as two essential learning models. Hence, in this chapter, field data via the Python ML tool are fed into the following supervised classification algorithms, whose models can be found in [62]:

- **Support Vector Machine:** SVM is a widely used ML classification algorithm, that finds the decision boundary between any two classes by creating a separation line (hyperplane), which divides the classes in the best possible manner, e.g., 4G or 5G.
- **Deep Neural Network:** DNN is a subset of ML, which makes the computation of a multilayer neural network structure, that can learn and make intelligent decisions on its own feasible. DNNs basically are of three types: 1.) Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), 2.) Recurrent neural network (RNN) and 3.) Convolutional neural network (CNN). MLP, just like every other type is based on an artificial neural network structure, and is a nonparametric estimator that can be used for classification and regression purposes. Since RNN and CNN had already been used in literature, hence, MLP is adopted in this study, where MLPClassifier setting used is stated as follows: `solver = 'adam', activation = 'relu', and hidden_layer_sizes=(64,64)`.
- **Extreme Gradient Boosting:** XGBoost is an ensemble, gradient-boosted decision tree (GBDT) ML algorithm. It is a scalable, end-to-end tree-boosting system, which comprises of a set of classification and regression trees (CART). It reduces the error rate as its trees grow one after another. Hence, its adoption as the proposed ML tool based on outstanding performance. XGBClassifier used is stated as follows: `tree_method = gpu_hist, enable_categorical = True, use_label_encoder = False`.

XGBoost's `gpu_hist` tree method enabled parallel processing across the 47 base stations, critical for maintaining <50ms decision latency during bus mobility.

It can be mathematically expressed as stated in equation 4.2 thus:

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{k=1}^K f_k x_i, f_k \in F \quad (4.2)$$

where y_i represents predicted output, K represents the number of trees, each f_k corresponds to an independent tree structure, and F stands for the set of all possible CARTs [75].

4.5 Field Data Measurement

4.5.1 Base Station Parameters

- **Frequency of operation:** It was observed during this study, that the UK-MNO utilized bands 1, 3, 7, 20, and bands n1, n3, n7, n20 for 4G LTE and 5G NR RATs respectively. Hence, these frequency bands according to 3GPP data [76], [77], have the following equivalent frequencies of operations: 2100, 1800, 2600, and 800 MHz respectively, all operating in frequency duplex division (FDD) mode.
- **Mode of transmission:** Frequency division duplexing (FDD) was utilized, and it is a method of establishing a full-duplex communication link that uses two different radio frequencies for transmitter and receiver operation. That is, the FDD operation usually assigns the transmitter and receiver to different communication channels.
- **Bandwidth:** It refers to the data transmission capacity of a communication channel in Hertz (Hz), that is, as bandwidth increases, more information per unit of time can pass through the channel. Hence, it connotes the maximum amount of spectrum available for data transmission on a communication channel in a specified time. Based on records from this study, since bands 1, 3, 7, and 20 are used in both 4G LTE and 5G NR, their equivalent bandwidths are 60, 75, 70, and 30 MHz respectively, as presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Base Stations Parameters

4G Band	5G Band	Frequency (MHz)	Bandwidth (MHz)	Duplex Mode
1	n1	2100	60	FDD
3	n3	1800	75	FDD
7	n7	2600	70	FDD
20	n20	800	30	FDD

$$Datarate = B \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{S}{N} \right) \quad (4.3)$$

where B denotes channel bandwidth measured in MHz.

S/N represents signal to noise ratio.

- Data rate: Bandwidth specification normally gives an idea of the capacity of a communication channel, but the data rate defines the actual (present) data transmission speed in the channel. Data rates are usually expressed in bits per second or bytes per second, hence data rate can be viewed as the actual data transmission speed in bits/sec.

As one of the benchmarks used in assessing the performance of a wireless communication channel, hence, its adoption as one of the measuring parameters. Therefore, computed data rates was based on the Shannon theorem formula. According to Shannon's theorem, the maximum data transmission rate possible in bits per second is given by the following equation: The Shannon equation 4.3 is then used to compute data rates experience of the travelling user, as he transverses across base stations.

4.5.2 Radio Measurement Parameters

The following measured parameters: RSRP, RSRQ, and RSSI [65], associated with 4G LTE; cell reference signal (CRS) were measured during the study:

Table 4.3: Signal Strength Indicator

SINR	Signal Strength
$\geq 20dB$	Excellent
13 dB - 20 dB	Good
0 dB - 13 dB	Fair to Poor
$\leq 0dB$	No signal

- Signal-to-noise and Interference ratio: Typical reporting ranges are as tabulated in Table 4.3. Values recorded were used in equation 4.3, to compute the data rate of 4G RATs.
- Reference Signal Received Power: RSRP typical reporting range is from -140 dBm to -44 dBm.
- Reference Signal Received Quality: RSRQ reporting range is from -19.5 dB to -3 dB.
- Received Signal Strength Indicator: RSSI is a measure of power and can be mathematically expressed as it relates with RSRP and RSRQ, as stated in equation 4.4:

$$RSSI = N * \left(\frac{RSRP}{RSRQ} \right) \quad (4.4)$$

where N is the number of resource blocks (RBs) per channel bandwidth.

However, the following parameters: SS-SINR, SS-RSRP, and SS-RSRQ associated with 5G networks; synchronization signal (SS) and channel state information (CSI), as defined by 3GPP [78] were measured as follows:

- Synchronization Signal Signal-to-noise and Interference Ratio (SS-SINR): Typical reporting ranges are as shown in Table 4.3. Measurements recorded were substituted in equation 4.3, to calculate the data rate of 5G RATs.

- Synchronization Signal Reference Signal Received Power (SS-RSRP). Its reporting range is from -140 dBm to -44 dBm.
- Secondary Synchronization Signal Reference Signal Received Quality (SS-RSRQ). Its reporting range is from -19.5 dB to -3 dB.
- RSSI can also be mathematically expressed as stated in equation 4.5:

$$RSSI = N * \left(\frac{SS - RSRP}{SS - RSRQ} \right) \quad (4.5)$$

where N is the number of resource blocks in the $RSSI$ measurement bandwidth.

4.5.3 Geo-Location Parameters

Geographical location (latitude, longitude) coordinates, are among other parameters measured and are as explained as follows:

- Latitude: This is the first number listed in geographical coordinates and its between -90 and 90 . Usually expressed in decimals. For instance latitude is 54.961628 in $(54.961628, -3.171315)$.
- Longitude: This is the second part of the geographical coordinates and it is between -180 and 180 . It is also expressed in decimals. For example longitude is -3.171315 in $(54.961628, -3.171315)$.

4.6 Multi-RAT Implementation

The following parameters: latitude, longitude, data rate, RSSI (which is common to 5G NR and 4G LTE in 5G NSA architecture, depending on the RAT a user is connected), and bandwidth (B_w), were compiled and saved as CSV (comma-separated values) file. The CSV format permits data to be saved in a table structured format (422 rows by 11 columns), suitable for ML tool analysis.

Algorithm 2 Machine Learning RAT Selection for Travelling user

Require: data
Ensure: RAT

```

begin
start timer
Load data (Busdata.csv) in CSV file format
Define input (X) and output (y) training and test data-sets
Call instance of a model: (DNN or XGBoost or SVM)
Split data:  $X - train, X - test, y - train, y - test$ 
 $X_{klmno} = \langle \text{latitude, longitude, data\_rate, RSSI, } B_w \rangle$ 
 $y_i = \langle 4G \text{ or } 5G \rangle$ 
Train the model: X-train, y-train
Define evaluation metrics
Total number of BS  $\leftarrow j$ 
BS  $\leftarrow 1$ 
while BS  $\leq j$  do
  if latitude =  $X_k$ , longitude =  $X_l$ , data_rate =  $X_m$ , RSSI =  $X_n$  and BW =  $X_o$  then
     $y_i \leftarrow 4G$ 
  else if latitude =  $X'_k$ , longitude =  $X'_l$ , data_rate =  $X'_m$ , RSSI =  $X'_n$  and BW =  $X'_o$ 
then
     $y_i \leftarrow 5G$ 
  end if
  Test the model:  $X - test$ 
  Predict (select) RAT:  $y - test$ 
  BS  $\leftarrow BS + 1$ 
end while
Score model
stop timer
Print results
end

```

As shown in Algorithm 2, the ML-based pseudo-code can be expressed in nested if-else if the sequence in a while loop, to compute parameters for all base stations, in order to obtain either 4G or 5G as an output; (Ensure) is defined as RAT, after checking input (Require) data parameters conditions.

The algorithm begins with a start timer, where the execution time of the algorithm is initialized. The CSV file named (Busdata.csv) is then imported (Load) into Jupyter Notebook; a ML environment programming language. Furthermore, the input data (latitude, longitude, data_rate, RSSI, B_w), and output data (RAT) which can either be 4G or 5G are defined as X and y parameters respectively. The input X and output y were further divided into training and testing datasets; X-train, y-train, and X-test, y-test respectively.

An instance of a model of DNN, or XGBoost, or SVM is also initiated (called) for prediction (selection) of a suitable RAT. The Geo-location (latitude, longitude), data_rate, RSSI, and B_w are used as input data (features); X_{klmno} to obtain the suitable RAT; $y_i = 4G$ or $5G$ (labeled output).

Thereafter, the model is then trained with the input and output training data-sets; X_{train} and y_{train} so as to learn data patterns and gain experience to be able to predict the y_{test} , meant to select either 4G or 5G RAT network.

In addition, the performance evaluation metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, and F-Score) of classification algorithms, and cross-validation scores used to evaluate and validate the model performance respectively are defined accordingly. The total number of base station (BS) is represented as j , this is followed by an initial value 1 assigned to BS for a while-loop operation, which is accomplished with $(BS = BS + 1)$ increment, until the total number of BS is computed. The input parameters are tested in the following if-else if conditions to select suitable RAT; y_i as 4G or 5G, after the ML model is tested with defined X_{test} ab initio. The evaluation and validation metrics are executed at the score model. After this, the timer stops, and results follow (Print results). Output results of training accuracy, execution time, RAT selected, performance evaluation, and validation metrics are displayed. The full dataset is available in [79].

4.7 Performance Evaluation

To achieve the second objective of this research work, performance evaluation of this study, is based on: the training accuracy of algorithms, execution time of each ML algorithm, classification metrics evaluation results, and cross-validation scores. During implementation, iteration was carried out ten times for each algorithm and an average of collated values were calculated to obtain performance evaluation results as highlighted in the following sections.

Table 4.4: Training Accuracy and Execution Rating

Algorithm	Training Accuracy	Execution Time	Execution Rating
SVM	0.6468	0.2803	Fast
DNN	0.9907	1.55	Lowest
XGBoost	0.9982	0.2767	Fastest

Figure 4.4: Training accuracy of algorithms.

4.7.1 Training Accuracy of Algorithms

During ML implementation, 80% of collated data were used as training data-set, while the remaining 20% were used as testing data-set for evaluation.

However, it was observed that SVM, DNN, and XGBoost have the following training accuracy: 0.6568, 0.9907, and 0.9982, respectively, as presented in Table 4.4. Hence, SVM is rated as having the lowest training accuracy, followed by DNN and XGBoost in ascending order respectively. The Fig. 4.4 shows x-axis represents the algorithms, and y-axis represents metric values of corresponding training accuracy of each algorithm.

4.7.2 Execution Time of Algorithms

Similarly, calculation of the execution time is done using the equation 4.6, to obtain the computational speed of each algorithm implored.

Figure 4.5: Execution time of algorithms.

$$execution_time = stop_time - start_time \quad (4.6)$$

It is observed from this study that SVM, DNN, and XGBoost have the following execution time: 0.2803, 1.55, and 0.2767 respectively. Therefore, they are rated accordingly from highest computational speed to the lowest as follows: XGBoost - fastest; showing its dexterity in computing, SVM - fast; displaying its high performance and DNN algorithm rated lowest, due to the number of layers naturally required to achieve good performance. Values collated are as presented in Table 4.4 and captured in Fig. 4.5. Where Fig. 4.5 x-axis represents the algorithms, and y-axis represents metric values of corresponding execution time of each algorithm.

4.7.3 Analysis of Evaluation Results

In general, the performance of the classification algorithms is analyzed in terms of accuracy (ACC), precision (P), recall (R), and F-score (F), which are calculated using the following formulas [80]:

- Accuracy: It is the ratio of correct predictions i.e. true positive (TP) results and true negative (TN) results, to the total number of instances evaluated. It can be

calculated from equation 4.7 as stated below:

$$ACC = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (4.7)$$

where FP stands for false positive (FP) and FN represents false negative (FN).

Observed results revealed the accuracy of algorithms as follows: SVM 0.6893, DNN 0.9929, and XGBoost 0.9964 respectively, as presented in Table 4.5.

- Precision: It is referred to as the number of true positive (TP) results divided by the number of all positive results, including results not correctly identified.

It can be calculated as stated in equation 4.8:

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (4.8)$$

During this study, the following precision values of algorithms were obtained: SVM 0.6880, DNN 0.9925, and XGBoost 0.9970, as shown in Table 4.5.

- Recall: It refers to the number of true positive (TP) results divided by the number of all sample datasets that should have been recognised as positive. It can be calculated as expressed in equation 4.9:

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (4.9)$$

Hence, the observed results are: SVM 0.8820, DNN 0.9920 and XGBoost 0.9940, as featured in Table 4.5.

- F-Score: It combines precision and recall as an overall measure of the model's

Table 4.5: Evaluation and Validation Metrics Values

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F-Score	Cross-Val
SVM	0.6893	0.6880	0.882	0.8100	0.7293
DNN	0.9929	0.9925	0.9920	0.9915	0.9906
XGBoost	0.9964	0.9970	0.9940	0.9955	0.9857

performance. It can be calculated as given in equation 4.10:

$$F = \frac{2}{1/P + 1/R} \quad (4.10)$$

The following values were recorded during this study: SVM 0.8100, DNN 0.9915, and XGBoost 0.9955, as revealed in Table 4.5.

Evaluation metrics; accuracy, precision, recall, and F-score are presented in Fig. 4.6, Fig. 4.7, Fig. 4.8 and Fig. 4.9, respectively, and further compared pictorially in Fig. 4.10. Where Fig. 4.6 x-axis represents the algorithms, and y-axis represents metric values of corresponding accuracy of each algorithm, Fig. 4.7 x-axis represents the algorithms, and y-axis represents metric values of corresponding precision of each algorithm, Fig. 4.8 x-axis represents the algorithms, and y-axis represents metric values of corresponding recall of each algorithm, and Fig. 4.9 x-axis stands for the algorithms, while the y-axis represents metric values of corresponding F-score of each algorithm.

Observation revealed that the XGBoost algorithm had the overall best evaluation performance, with DNN coming at close range in performance to XGBoost, while SVM took the least among the three algorithms used for implementation. Hence, this study proposes and adopts XGBoost model, for RAT selection in multiple base station scenario.

4.8 Validation Metric

Validation of implored models were further evaluated, with cross-validation score metrics; whose model is already described in [62]. The cross-validation score metric is used in

Figure 4.6: Accuracy evaluation metric of algorithms.

Figure 4.7: Precision evaluation metric of algorithms.

ML to evaluate the proficiency of any ML model on unseen future data. This is achieved by using a limited sample of training dataset to evaluate the model performance in totality, when used to make predictions on dataset not used during initial training.

The numerical results are shown in Table 4.5, where it is observed that SVM, DNN, and XGBoost have the following cross-validation score values: 0.7293, 0.9906, and 0.9857 respectively. Both DNN and XGBoost displayed remarkable results as shown in Fig. 4.11.

DNN has the ability to learn from data and generalize while XGBoost is fast in interpreting when handling large-sized datasets. Meanwhile, the SVM algorithm is not suitable for large and noisy datasets.

Figure 4.8: Recall evaluation metric of algorithms.

Figure 4.9: F-Score evaluation metric of algorithms.

4.9 Conclusion

In this chapter, the RAT selection algorithm for efficient resource allocation for public bus traveling user(s), utilising multiple 5G NSA base stations, is presented to achieve the second objective of this research.

Supervised learning algorithms; SVM, DNN, and XGBoost, were deployed to select an appropriate RAT. The geographical location (latitude and longitude) of a traveling user, data rate experienced by the user from the network, network coverage in terms of RSSI, and available bandwidth on each RAT, were used as parameters for RAT selection. Collated live 5G NSA data were divided into training and testing datasets.

Figure 4.10: Comparison of metrics evaluation of algorithms.

Figure 4.11: Cross validation score of algorithms.

The training (input) datasets were used to train models of the supervised ML algorithms deployed; SVM, DNN, and XGBoost. Furthermore, the trained models were tested with input test datasets to predict or select the appropriate RAT (4G/5G) as labeled output. Evaluation of results showed a measure of the accuracy of the proposed model; XGBoost at the optimal level of 99.64%, which was further cross-validated at 98.57%, when compared with other algorithms for its effectiveness on future data and mitigation ability.

Therefore, recommended for optimization purposes in multiple base station environments, for proper resource allocation on the part of phone manufacturers, vendors, and service providers that will impact users' experience positively, in order to assist the continually increasing request of network devices, which will consequently enhance network efficiency. This study is limited to a traveling user in a public bus traversing a defined route. However, while effective for fixed routes, future work should address dynamic path variations through reinforcement learning-based adaptation.

4.10 Chapter Summary

Based on the study presented above, this chapter has accomplished the second set objective, by equally using ML approach for Multi-RAT selection in 5G NSA network, by a travelling user in a public bus. Consequently, the following chapter deviates from 5G NSA, by addressing the third set objective, which requires 5G stand alone. Similarly, a ML integrable optimiser, is used in the following chapter, for optimal RAT selection and datarate allocation in 5G SA scenario, applicable in 5G and beyond networks.

Chapter 5

Machine Learning Enabled Optimal RAT Selection in 5G SA Networks

5.1 Introduction

The increasing complexity, heterogeneous nature, and stipulated service requirements of 5G networks, have turned the usual procedures of network operation and optimisation presently unsuitable. Hence, Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) and hardware vendors have been equipping their products with ML based utilities to attain optimal set objectives. This chapter proposes a MILP-based optimisation framework for joint RAT selection and data rate allocation in 5G SA networks, considering pathloss, bandwidth, and user-load constraints. The optimisation problem is formed as a non-convex, nonlinear type, with available bandwidth, number of existing users on base stations, location of users, and pathloss between users and base stations considered as constraints. These constraints are relaxed to a mixed integer linear programming (MILP) problem, and then solved using Gurobi optimiser for appropriate base station RAT selection, and users' data rate allocation, which are required for efficient network bandwidth utilisation. Performance evaluation is carried out in comparison with Heuristic algorithm results used as benchmark, where the proposed optimiser showed performance proximity of 4% difference, to benchmarked algorithm results.

5.2 Chapter Background

Conventional methods of network operation and optimisation approaches; (e.g. geometric), require appreciable level of expertise, and theoretical assumptions, which often will not be accurate, and hence, not applicable in real-life situations. In order to ameliorate the effects of these traditional methods, hardware sellers and MNOs currently enable their equipment with ML-based features to enhance mobile networks with intelligence required to achieve optimum operational goal. Since 5G NR is expected to operate in FR1 band; (410 – 7125 MHz), and FR2 - millimeter wave (mmWave) band; (24250 MHz – 52600 MHz). Hence, due to its short wave length, it will require new architectural and radio resource management tasks of many communication devices like cellular systems, vehicular application (V2V, V2X, V2I), radar, and satellite communications.

Therefore, based on perspective of capacity, and coverage maximisation, it is suggested that 4G and 5G are co-deployed to ensure uninterrupted coverage and minimise infrastructure, planning and optimisation costs [59]. This resulted in the adoption of the 5G Multi-RAT architecture as depicted in Fig. 5.1 in this chapter. It comprises of 5G SA base stations (gNBs), that address the three ITU-defined 5G applications: uRLLC, mMTC, and eMBB, respectively. Along with 4G SA base stations (eNBs), that focus on eMBB based on 3GPP Release 15 standard. Typically, 5G SA system comprises of UE, RAN; tagged new radio (NR), and the 5G core (5GC). However, the 4G SA system, comprises of UE, RAN; tagged LTE, and the 4G core; EPC [10]. 5G SA equipment access its core network (5GC) via control signalling free of 4G network. Hence, interoperability between 5G and 4G networks are attained via their core networks.

This is used to implement inter-RAT handover, and/or redirection depending on different use cases with less latency [12]. Meanwhile, optimisation can be defined as a method of making best or most effective use of resource(s) or scenario. In 5G wireless network, optimisation can be divided into two categories: engineering optimisation, which is carried out at the initial stage of network setup, and operation-maintenance optimisation; which is done on daily routine, for smooth operation [81]. A novel ML based optimiser, that addresses these two aforementioned categories is hereby proposed.

Figure 5.1: 5G Multi-RAT Architecture.

Optimisation implementation procedure typically involves three basic stages: (i) Modelling; which is the process of expressing the problem in mathematical terms. The modelling stage further comprises of: (a) Defining the objective function; a quantitative measure of performance of the system intended to be optimised, (b) Identifying variables to be optimised, i.e., the components of the system; whose values are intended to be found. (c) Setting up constraints limits. Constraints are the functions that define the relationships among the variables, these functions specify the acceptable values for the variables. (ii) Determining the problem type; this is the process of optimisation model categorisation.

An optimisation problem can either be: (a) Continuous or Discrete (b) Constrained or Unconstrained, (c) Convex or Concave (Non-convex), (d) Linear or Nonlinear, (e) Differentiable or Non-differentiable, (f) Stochastic or Deterministic, or a combination of any of the categories (i.e. combinatorial). In this scenario, the optimisation problem objective function aims to connect users with appropriate RAT, and optimise resource (users' data rate) allocation, in a 5G network of multiple base stations and users scenario. It has been identified as non-convex, nonlinear optimisation problem, with available bandwidth, number of existing users on base stations, location of users, and pathloss between users and base stations as constraints, which are not used yet in previous literature.

(iii) The last stage is selecting the optimisation tool to solve the problem, which is a function of the problem type. Generally, a non-convex, nonlinear problem, is NP-hard, hence, this optimisation problem has to be relaxed to MILP problem, and then solved with a novel and fast (MILP) problem solver; Gurobi optimiser [82], which has also not been used for optimal RAT selection in literature. Its results are compared with Heuristic optimisation method's; which is adjudged to be very fast in making good guesses or decision of optimal solution, since it considers limited or no assumptions about the optimisation problem. However, the proposed optimiser, with aforementioned constraints considered, still records a 4% performance increment over Heuristic method's results during evaluation.

5.2.1 Study Methodology

Signal parameters of multiple 5G network model as depicted in Fig. 5.2, consisting of multiple 4G LTE base stations; (BS1, BS6), and 5G NR base stations; (BS2, BS3, BS4, BS5), serving multiple users; (User1, User2,..., User16), are used for the optimisation of data rate of each user, with respect to available bandwidth, number of existing users on base stations, location of users, and pathloss between users and base stations as constraints. Generally, optimisation problem can either involve minimising or maximising an objective function, by methodologically defining input variables. Hence, the following efficient methods were adopted to solve this maximisation problem:

- Data relationship function that relates data rate R_{ij} to transmit power P_i and pathloss L_{ij} based on Shannon-Hartley channel model is defined. Where maximum (peak) data rate in bits per second, is expressed by equation 5.1:

$$R_{ij} = B \log_2(1 + SINR) \quad (5.1)$$

where B denotes channel bandwidth measured in MHz.

$SINR$ represents signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio.

- Reformulating the constraints involving user assignment into linear inequalities using binary variables. These variables represent whether any user is connected to any specific base station or not. This condition is necessary for using MILP solver chosen.
- For a guaranteed optimal solution, a specialized MILP solver (Gurobi) is used to find optimal solution, while adhering to defined constraints.
- Heuristic algorithm is implemented for faster execution time, and its results compared with Gurobi's results. Since it offers approximate solutions that are often computationally faster than MILP.
- The chosen solver was run with the defined functions and specified constraints. Analyse the resulting user assignments, and data rates for overall network bandwidth utilisation.
- Finally, performance metrics are used to determine solver model proficiency, as presented under performance evaluation and validation section.

This chapter is organised as follows: section 5.3 features system model and problem formulation, section 5.4 highlights optimisation implementation and results, while section 5.5 elucidates performance evaluation and validation. Thereafter, section 5.6 presents chapter's conclusion.

5.3 System Model and Problem Formulation

5.3.1 System Model

A Multi-Base Station RAT architecture model of 5G SA networks, which is both user-centric and network-centric as depicted in Fig. 5.1. Where UEs due to their transmit power P_i , and location i.e., distance d from base station, are either connected with 5G SA or 4G LTE SA base stations, denoted as gNBs and eNBs respectively.

Furthermore, from network point of view, UEs are also associated with either 5G SA base stations or 4G LTE SA base stations, based on available bandwidth B_j at each base station, number of existing users N_{ij} on each base station, and pathloss L_{ij} between users and base stations respectively.

A dense urban environment, where a UE at LoS (line of sight) can associate with a base station at a time is considered. Hence, Urban Macro (UMa) and Urban Micro (UMi) according to 3GPP notation [83], are used as pathloss models. The Multi-RAT architecture is deployed, where Poisson Point Processes (PPP) distribution densities of Ω_i and Ω_j for users and base stations respectively are assumed. While 4G RAT and 5G NR RAT represent 4G LTE SA radio access technology and 5G SA radio access technology, respectively. Therefore, let the UE to be connected with any base station (BS) be denoted as $U = U_1, U_2, \dots, U_i$, hence, the association matrix between the BS and user U_i , in this model is denoted as $X = X_{11}, X_{22}, \dots, X_{ij}$. The association variable existing between user U_i and BS, is denoted as X_{ij} , and could either be binary 0 or 1.

Moreover, to carry out connectivity operation, where the set of all achievable association operation (x), to choose between 4G RAT or 5G NR RAT in all base stations, is represented as: $\{x_0, x_1\}$. Where x_0 stand for the action of not connecting to a RAT, while x_1 represents choosing one of the available RATs for connectivity. In addition, assign the coverage level of the network C of individual RAT examined as $\{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_j\}$, based on the assumption that communication is reliable. Meanwhile, the data rate R of individual RAT is also taken into account as $R = R_{11}, R_{22}, \dots, R_{ij}$. Then, the connection status S of user can be defined by the vector of features as follows: $\{P_i, B_j, \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_j\}, N_{ij}, R_{ij}, L_{ij}\}$.

Therefore, the system status vector (S) would be utilised to decide the most suitable RAT connectivity operation: $X \in x_0, x_1$; that stands for the event of not connecting to a base station (RAT) or using the other available suitable base station (RAT) for connectivity.

5.3.2 Problem Formulation

The optimisation objective is to maximise data rate for set of users ($i = 1, 2, \dots, I$) in a 5G network of set of base stations ($j = 1, 2, \dots, J$).

Table 5.1: System Model Abbreviations with Description

Abbreviation	Description
U_i	User i
W_i	Weight assigned to user i
x_{ij}	Binary decision variable
R_{ij}	Data rate of user i
U_j	Maximum no of users served by base station j
B_j	Available bandwidth at base station j
P_i	Maximum transmit power allocated to user i
L_{ij}	Pathloss of user i and base station j

Then, formulate the problem as a 5G user association for RAT selection, with the aim of maximizing weighted (W) data rate.

$$\text{Maximize : } \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J W_i * R_{ij} \quad (5.2)$$

where W_i denotes weight assigned to user i (unitless) and R_{ij} stands for data rate of user i , when associated with base station j in bits per second.

Optimisation can be viewed as a resultant maximum or minimum function evaluation problem, following the definition of set of input variables to an objective function. Hence, the variables are: x_{ij} ; binary decision variable (1 if user i is connected with a base station j , 0 otherwise) and R_{ij} . Where equation 5.2 is the objective function intended to be optimised, and the following conditions that must be satisfied are called constraints.

Normally, optimisation problems can be stated as either unconstrained or constrained functions. Unconstrained signifies the variables can take up any value, that is, no restriction, whereas constrained connotes that the variables are limited to specific values within a range. The constraints are as highlighted as follows:

- Constraint 1: User Association: Each user can only be attached with one base station at a time, as stated in equation 5.3.

$$\sum_{i=1}^I (x_{ij}) = 1, \forall i \quad (5.3)$$

- Constraint 2: Available Bandwidth: The total data rate assigned to users attached with a base station should not be more than the available bandwidth, as specified in equation 5.4.

$$\sum_{j=1}^J (R_{ij} * x_{ij}) \leq B_j, \forall j, \quad (5.4)$$

where B_j is the available bandwidth at base station j in bits per second.

- Constraint 3: Number of Existing Users: The amount of users attached to any base station cannot exceed its capacity, as stated in equation 5.5.

$$\sum_{j=1}^J (x_{ij}) \leq U_j, \forall j, \quad (5.5)$$

where U_j is maximum number of users served by base station j .

- Constraint 4: Pathloss and Location of Users: The data rate of a user depends on the path loss existing in-between the user and the serving base station. Hence, the data rate R_{ij} is declared as function of transmit power, and Pathloss, as expressed in equation 5.6.

$$R_{ij} \leq (P_i \cdot L_{ij}) * x_{ij}, \forall ij \quad (5.6)$$

where P_i is maximum transmit power allocated to user i in Watts (W) and L_{ij} is the Pathloss between user i and base station j in decibel (dB). Path loss as measured in dB, is basically the decrease recorded between the transmitted power and the received power. It can be viewed as the loss that the signal experiences, as it radiates through the wireless channel from transmitter to receiver. That is, the reduction in signal strength as it travels through a wireless channel.

Pathloss depends on many parameters, such as distance of user from base station (location of user), frequency of operation, antenna gain, height of base station, height of receiving antenna and propagation environments (rural, suburban, urban and dense urban). Hence pathloss evaluation is essential for designing and optimizing wireless networks.

Since this constraint influences the coverage, capacity, and quality of service between the users and base stations, therefore, the propagation models based on the 3GPP channel model are adopted, for both Urban Macro (UMa) and Urban Micro (UMi) scenarios, as stated in equation 5.7, and equation 5.8, respectively, when the propagation channel is free of obstructions [83].

UMa-LoS:

$$PL_{UMa-LoS} = \begin{cases} PL_1 & 10m \leq d \leq d_{BP}. \\ PL_2 & d_{BP} \leq d \leq 5km. \end{cases} \quad (5.7a)$$

$$PL_1 = 28.0 + 22\log_{10}d + 20\log_{10}f_c \quad (5.7b)$$

$$PL_2 = 28.0 + 40\log_{10}d + 20\log_{10}f_c - 9\log_{10}f_c - 0.6(h_{UT} - 1.5) \quad (5.7c)$$

UMi-LoS:

$$PL_{UMi-LoS} = \begin{cases} PL_1 & 10m \leq d \leq d_{BP}. \\ PL_2 & d_{BP} \leq d \leq 5km. \end{cases} \quad (5.8a)$$

$$PL_1 = 32.4 + 21\log_{10}d + 20\log_{10}f_c \quad (5.8b)$$

$$PL_2 = 32.4 + 40\log_{10}d + 20\log_{10}f_c - 9.5\log_{10}((d_{BP})^2 + (h_{BS} - h_{UT})^2) \quad (5.8c)$$

Figure 5.2: Multi-RAT Architecture of 4G LTE BS1 & BS6 and 5G NR BS2, BS3, BS4 & BS5 serving Multiple users (1-16).

where:

f_c = center frequency in (Hz)

d = distance between user and base station

d_{BP} = breaking point distance

h_{BS} = height of base station

h_{UT} = the height of user terminal

Pathloss evaluation is carried out as described in [83] and [84] respectively, and pathloss values of each user are obtained relative to each base station accordingly.

- **Constraint 5: Binary constraint:** This is the binary constraint that connotes that the variable (x_{ij}) must be either be 0 or 1, as stated in equation 5.9. That is, 1 when user i is provided connectivity from base station j , or 0 when it is otherwise.

$$x_{ij} = \{0, 1\}, \forall ij \quad (5.9)$$

Having expressed the problem by defining the objective function, identifying variables to be optimised and setting up constraints limits, there is need to determine the problem type as aforementioned.

From the objective function and constraints stated, it can be deduced that, since relationship between transmit power P_i , pathloss L_{ij} is typically nonlinear, and from data rate R_{ij} ; Shannon-Hartley theorem [85], which include logarithmic terms, hence the stated problem is a nonlinear optimisation type. Moreover, the binary constraints; x_{ij} is an integer, and data rate; R_{ij} is a continuous variable, these introduce another layer of complexity compared to continuous optimisation problems.

Therefore, it can be concluded that; the stated objective is a constrained, non-convex, nonlinear optimisation problem. A non-convex optimisation problem is any problem where the objective or any of the constraints are non-convex. In order to solve such complex combinatorial problem, that is NP-hard, the problem is relaxed to a MILP type as done in [52], and then choose a solver, to obtain feasible solutions. Therefore, in this optimisation problem, feasible solution that also maximises the stated objective function is the optimal solution. The objective function and constraints can be re-written as a MILP for a 5G user association i.e., RAT selection problem with the aim of maximising weighted data rate as follows, in equation 5.10:

Objective function: Maximize data rate (R) of all users i

$$\text{Maximize : } \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J W_i * R_{ij} \quad (5.10)$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{i=1}^I (x_{ij}) = 1, \forall i \quad (5.10a)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^J (R_{ij} * x_{ij}) \leq B_j, \forall j, \quad (5.10b)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^J (x_{ij}) \leq U_j, \forall j, \quad (5.10c)$$

$$R_{ij} \leq (P_i \cdot L_{ij}) * x_{ij}, \forall ij \quad (5.10d)$$

$$x_{ij} = \{0, 1\}, \forall ij \quad (5.10e)$$

where the binary constraint; the association variable (x_{ij}) must be binary (0 or 1), for all users i and base stations j . The optimisation problem 5.10 is nonlinear, mixed integer maximisation problem, that determine the assignment of each user to the best base station. That is, RAT selection based on available bandwidth at each base station, number of existing users on base stations, location of users and pathloss between users and base stations. The objective is to ensure the required data rates for all users, while maximising weighted bandwidth at user's disposal for optimal data rate.

5.4 Implementation and Results

During the implementation exercise, the proposed optimiser runs on win64 - Windows 10.0 system, Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8650U, CPU 1.90 GHz model. The Gurobi Optimizer version 11.0.1, was implemented via Python 3.6 in Anaconda, using default MILP parameters except for MIPGap=0.01 to ensure solution quality. Normally, implementation requires using optimiser's Application Programming Interface (API) or file format in Anaconda-Python as used in this chapter, to define the sets, parameters, variables, objective function, and constraints as shown in Algorithm 3. Then, use the solver's function to solve the defined MILP model, and consequently extract results. The solver will then provide the optimal values for the decision variables x_{ij} , which indicates the user association with base stations. From this and the R_{ij} definition, the solver will calculate the data rates of total weighted bandwidth and display the association i.e., RAT selection of each user to specific base station.

5.4.1 Proposed (Gurobi) Optimisation Algorithm

As presented in Algorithm 3.

- Import the Gurobi library (GRB), then define number of users and number of base stations as: ($num_users = 16$) and ($num_stations = 6$) respectively.
- Assign equal weights for all users to achieve fairness in bandwidth allocation as: ($user_weights = [1, 1, \dots, 1]$).
- Assign maximum transmit power of 0.1 watts per user as: ($max_power = 0.1$).
- Create a list of Pathloss between each user and base station (dB). $pathloss = [ij]$.
- In addition, available bandwidth in each base station is specified in Hertz as: ($available_bandwidth = [50\text{MHz}, 90\text{MHz}, 80\text{MHz}, 75\text{MHz}, 70\text{MHz}, 60\text{MHz}]$) respectively.
- Define the maximum number of users that can be connected to each base station as: ($max_users_per_station = [3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3]$), this specifies base station capacity.
- Then define the model as: ($model = Model("5G_User_Association")$).
- This is followed by defining the variables, where x_{ij} is the binary variable for user association and R_{ij} is a continuous variable for data rates.
- Set objective to maximise the weighted sum of data rates for all users as:
($model.setObjective(GRB.MAXIMIZE)$).
- Add constraints representing (i) User association limitations: i.e., each user can only be associated with one base station at a time, (ii) Base station capacity for j , (iii) Available bandwidth for j , and (iv) Data rate relationship with pathloss.
- Then solve the model as: ($model.optimize()$).
- Results are finally displayed for user association and data rates as: ($print("User i is associated with base station j with data rate $R[i, j]$ Mbps")$), if solution is feasible, otherwise $print("Model infeasible or failed to solve")$, if model is infeasible.

Algorithm 3 Optimisation using proposed MILP Solver**Require:** data(num_users, num_stations, max_power, pathloss, available_bandwidth, max_users_per_station)**Ensure:** User Association, Data rate

```

procedure GRB ▷ Import (Gurobi) Library
  Define parameters num_users and num_stations
  Assign user_weights for each user
  Assign max_power for all users
  Create a list of pathloss[i][j]
  Specify available_bandwidth at each base station
  Define max_users_per_station
  Create a 5G User_Association model
  Define variables  $x_{ij}$  and  $R_{ij}$ 
  for i in range num_users do
    for j in range num_stations do
       $x[i, j] = \text{GRB.BINARY}$ 
       $R[i, j] = \text{GRB.CONTINUOUS}$ 
    end for
  end for
  for i in range num_users do
    for j in range num_stations do
       $user\_weights[i] * R[i, j]$ 
      model.setObjective(GRB.MAXIMIZE)
    end for
  end for
  for i in range num_users do
    addConstr(sum( $x[i, j]$  for j in range num_stations)
  end for
  for j in range num_stations do
    addConstr(sum( $x[i, j]$  for i in range num_users)  $\leq$  max_users_per_station[j]
  end for
  for j in range num_stations do
    addConstr(sum( $R[i, j] * x[i, j]$  for i in range num_users)  $\leq$  available_bandwidth[j]
  end for
  for i in range num_users do
    for j in range num_stations do
       $data\_rate = available\_bandwidth / pathloss[i][j]$ 
    end for
  end for
  Solve the model for optimisation (model.optimize())
  if model.status == GRB.OPTIMAL then
    for i in range num_users do
      for j in range num_stations do
        if  $x[i, j].x > 0.99$ 
          end for
        end for
        print("Model feasible")
        print("User i is associated with Base Station j with data rate  $R[i, j]$ ")
      else
        print("Model infeasible or failed to solve")
      end if
    end for
  end if
end procedure

```

5.4.2 Optimisation using Heuristic Algorithm

As shown in Algorithm 4. Here, optimisation is implemented using the Heuristic algorithm, for weighted user association, in a 5G network scenario. This algorithm involves iterative assignment of users to base stations based on the constraints aforementioned. Although Heuristic algorithm sometimes does not guarantee finding the absolute optimal solution, they often provide near-optimal results with significantly less processing time. The following outlines the Heuristic algorithm used to solve the 5G user association problem for RAT selection, with the aim of maximizing weighted data rate for users:

- Step 1: Input parameters:
 - Number of base stations is defined as *num_stations*.
 - Then assign *user_weights* for each user.
 - Define maximum number of users per base station as *max_users_per_station*.
 - Define the Pathloss evaluated values.
 - Also, define weighted user association as *weighted_user_association* for *available_bandwidth*, *max_users_per_station*, and *user_weights* respectively.
- Step 2: Initialization:
 - The algorithm then initializes an empty list *user_association* to store the association between users and base stations.
 - It further sets all elements in *user_association* to negative, indicating no association yet.
- Step 3: Sort users by weight.
 - Then, algorithm sorts users in descending order of their weights *user_weights*. This prioritizes users with higher weights during association.
- Step 4: Iteration:
 - The algorithm further iterates through users in sorted order for each user *i*. Then,
 - Calculate the pathloss (L_{ij}) to all base stations *j*.
 - Calculate the weighted data rate ($W_i * R_{ij}$) for each base station *j*.
- Step 5: Find best base station (RAT selection):

Identify the base station *j* that offers the highest weighted data rate ($W_i * R_{ij}$) for user *i*, considering the following constraints:

 - The base station *j* has available bandwidth.

- The number of users associated with base station j is less than the maximum capacity.
- Step 6: Update Association:
 - If a suitable base station is found meeting constraints conditions, update the *user_association* of $itoj$.
This signifies user i is associated with base station j .
- Step 7: Repeat Iteration:
 - Go back to step 4 and iterate through remaining users, until all users are associated with a base station or no suitable base station can be found for a user.
- Step 8: Assign *weighted_user_association* parameters to *user_association*.
 - Assign *weighted_user_association* parameters (*available_bandwidth*, *max_users_per_station* and *user_weights*) to *user_association*.
 - print *user_association*.

This will show base station assigned to each user, i.e., *user_association* list, will now contain the association among users and their assigned base station j (RAT selection) as outputs, plus data rate allocated respectively.

5.4.3 Results and Discussion

Simulation was carried out using Python programming language version 3.6, where the Multi-RAT architecture used in this chapter as shown in Fig. 5.2, is deployed over an area of 5000×5000 meters as depicted. It comprises of two 4G LTE base stations: BS1 and BS6 (colour blue), with assigned operational frequencies of 2.6 GHz, and four 5G NR base stations: BS2, BS3, BS4, and BS5 (colour green), operating at 3.6 GHz respectively. The base stations serve multiple (sixteen) users: User1, User2, ..., User16 (colour black).

Algorithm 4 Optimisation using Heuristic Algorithm**Require:** data(num_stations, available_bandwidth, max_users_per_station, pathloss)**Ensure:** User Association, Data rate

```

Define num_stations
Assign user_weights for each user
Define available_bandwidth at each base station
Define max_users_per_station
Define evaluatedpathloss
Define weighted_user_asso for available_bandwidth, max_users_per_station, user_weights
user_association = [-1] * len(user_weights)
Sort users by weight in descending order
sorted_user_indices = user_weights
for i in sorted_user_indices do
    best_station = -1
    best_weighted_rate = 0
end for
for j in num_stations do
    pathloss_val = pathloss(f_carrier)
    estimated_rate = available_bandwidth/pathloss_val
end for
if available_bandwidth[j] >= estimated_rate then
    weighted_rate = user_weights[i] * estimated_rate
end if
if weighted_rate > best_weighted_rate then
    best_station = j
    best_weighted_rate = weighted_rate
end if
if best_station != -1 then
    user_association[i] = best_station
    available_bandwidth -= estimated_rate
    return user_association
    user_association = weighted_user_association
    print user_association
end if

```

Where a Poisson Point Processes (PPP) distribution densities of Ω_i and Ω_j for users and base stations are assumed respectively. A dense urban environment is also considered, where users are positioned 10m apart in both horizontal and vertical axes. Each user has a pre-set transmit power P_i of 0.1 watts for fairness, and can only connect with a single base station at a time. Hence, Urban Macro (UMa); equation 5.7b and Urban Micro (UMi); equation 5.8b are used to evaluate pathloss L_{ij} between users and respective base stations. Bandwidths of each base station are set to 50MHz, 90MHz, 80MHz, 75MHz, 70MHz and 60MHz, with corresponding SINR relative to users' location.

Generally, connectivity of users to base stations can either be through optimal strategy; which is an exhaustive search process from users, among all potential base stations. However, this is not practicable, as it also consumes time. Connectivity can also be through SINR based strategy, where a user is served via base station with highest SINR value. This can also be referred to as classical approach [49]. Although, user association in a Multi-RAT network scenario of many frequency bands is complex, and determining the optimal user association is generally a combinatorial optimisation problem.

It also relies on the SINR all users to every base station, the instantaneous load at each base station, the choices of other users in the network, and possibly other constraints such as the requirement to utilize same base station and standard in both downlink and uplink [86], and pathloss, which has not been used as a constraint in literature. Hence, the adoption of the proposed user association (MILP) software for implementation, which will also be the first time to be used for user association or RAT selection in literature. Finally, Gurobi solver records optimal feasible solutions at 9.94×10^6 , 1.79×10^7 , 1.59×10^7 , 1.49×10^7 , 1.39×10^7 , 1.19×10^7 , while Heuristic feasible solutions are found at 9.59×10^6 , 1.73×10^7 , 1.53×10^7 , 1.44×10^7 , 1.34×10^7 , 1.15×10^7 respectively as presented in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2: Optimisation Solutions

Bandwith (MHz)	Gurobi	Heuristic
50	9.94E+06	9.59E+06
90	1.79E+07	1.73E+07
80	1.59E+07	1.53E+07
75	1.49E+07	1.44E+07
70	1.39E+07	1.34E+07
60	1.19E+07	1.15E+07

The maximised data rate of users, when bandwidths of 50MHz, 90MHz, 80MHz, 75MHz, 70MHz and 60MHz bandwidths are assigned to the base stations (1-6) are as tabulated in Table 5.3 and presented in Fig. 5.3 respectively.

Table 5.3: Maximised Data rate at various Bandwidth

User_ID	50 MHz	90 MHz	80 MHz	75 MHz	70 MHz	60 MHz
User 1	857.63	1543.74	1372.21	1286.45	200.69	1029.16
User 2	770.18	1386.32	1232.29	1155.27	1078.25	924.21
User 3	726.74	1308.14	1162.79	1090.12	1017.44	872.09
User 4	631.31	1136.36	1010.10	946.97	883.84	757.58
User 5	618.28	1112.90	989.24	927.41	865.59	741.93
User 6	607.75	1093.96	972.41	911.63	850.86	729.31
User 7	591.23	1064.21	945.96	886.84	827.72	709.47
User 8	584.59	1052.26	935.34	876.89	818.43	701.51
User 9	578.70	1041.67	925.93	868.06	810.19	694.44
User 10	594.04	1069.26	950.46	891.05	831.65	712.84
User 11	589.69	1061.45	943.51	884.54	825.57	707.63
User 12	585.69	1054.23	937.10	878.53	819.96	702.82
User 13	556.73	1002.12	890.77	835.10	779.42	668.08
User 14	553.28	995.91	885.25	829.92	774.59	663.94
User 15	550.12	990.21	880.18	825.17	770.16	660.14
User 16	544.37	979.86	870.99	816.53	762.11	653.14

From above, it can be deduced that data rates allocated to users vary based on constraints used, however data rates increase as the bandwidth assigned also increases, which justify the efficacy of the proposed optimiser.

Figure 5.3: Total maximised data rate of users.

5.5 Performance Evaluation and Validation

The Fig. 5.4, shows the comparison chart of the utilised optimisation techniques, where the solutions of Gurobi optimiser and Heuristic method as presented in Table 5.2 are plotted on the y-axis, against assigned bandwidth values on the x-axis. The chart reveals the degree of closeness in optimisation solution gotten during evaluation, with a 4% performance increment over Heuristic algorithm, as shown in Fig. 5.4. This is further validated using percentage error and standard deviation as metrics to authenticate proposed optimiser's accuracy and efficacy.

5.5.1 Percentage Error

Percentage error (PE) is used to evaluate the degree of closeness or how far away values are to the benchmark. Smaller values denote closeness to baseline, while higher values connote values are far away from the benchmark. PE formula is as given in equation 5.11.

$$PE = \left(\frac{\text{accepted_value} - \text{experimental_value}}{\text{accepted_value}} \right) * 100\% \quad (5.11)$$

Using values in Table 5.4, the mean of the Gurobi (1.41×10^7) is found, and substituted as accepted value, while the mean of Heuristic solution (1.36×10^7) is substituted as experimental value, and PE is evaluated at 0.04 (4%), which validates results obtained as plotted in Fig. 5.4.

Table 5.4: Standard Deviation Table

Gurobi	Heuristic	Variance1	Variance2
9.94E+06	9.59E+06	1.72E+13	1.60E+13
1.79E+07	1.73E+07	3.20E+14	2.98E+14
1.59E+07	1.53E+07	2.53E+14	2.35E+14
1.49E+07	1.44E+07	2.22E+14	2.07E+14
1.39E+07	1.34E+07	1.94E+14	1.80E+14
1.19E+07	1.15E+07	1.42E+14	1.32E+14
1.41E+07	1.36E+07	1.91E+14	1.78E+14

Figure 5.4: Gurobi and Heuristic optimisers solutions.

5.5.2 Using Standard Deviation

The mean values of columns Gurobi and Heuristic are first calculated as $1.41E+07$ (1.41×10^7), and $1.36E+07$ (1.36×10^7) as shown in Table 5.4, respectively, then the calculation of the squared deviations from the mean, to obtain deviation.

Further, the variance is calculated by adding the squared deviations from the mean for all values in the Gurobi and Heuristic columns, and then divided by the number of values ($N = 6$), to obtain Variance1 and Variance2 respectively. Then, standard deviation is calculated, by taking square root of variance of both variables. The ratio of the standard deviation of Variance1/Variance2 is then evaluated, where the value 1.04 or 104% is obtained. This result obtained further validates Fig. 5.4, where Gurobi displays 4% performance increment over Heuristic method.

5.6 Conclusion

In this chapter, a novel ML based solution for a 5G network and beyond RAT selection and data rate optimisation problem is presented. The architecture comprises of multiple base stations serving multiple users. The optimisation objective is to maximise data rate of users, while available bandwidth, number of existing users on base stations, location of users and pathloss between users and base stations are considered as constraints. The optimisation problem equations was formed as non-convex, nonlinear type, hence, the constraints were relaxed to a MILP, and eventually solved with Gurobi optimiser and Heuristic algorithm respectively. Guaranteed optimal values of chosen solver showed feasible solutions. The results obtained displayed appropriate RAT selection of base stations by users, with maximised data rate allocation to each user respectively. Evaluation of the MILP solver's results showed a 4% performance increment over Heuristic method's results, which depicts the efficacy of the proposed solution. Therefore, recommended for RAT selection technique and network data rate optimisation required for efficient and effective network bandwidth utilisation in 5G and beyond networks. Although, simulation results demonstrate theoretical efficacy, future work should validate against 3GPP-compliant field trials to assess real-world performance under mobility and interference. Meanwhile, this study assumes static user distributions and fixed transmit power. Dynamic scenarios with vehicular mobility or adaptive power control also remain open challenges.

5.7 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, the third set objective has been accomplished, using 5G SA scenario, for optimal RAT selection between 5G SA and 4G SA networks. A novel ML based optimiser is used for appropriate RAT selection, and data rate allocation for mobile users. Hence, all the set objectives have been accomplished, and published accordingly. Therefore, the following chapter presents overall summary of study, and a concise record of future work.

Chapter 6

Overall Conclusion and Future Work

6.1 Conclusion

In this thesis, the researcher presented machine learning algorithm for effective RAT selection and efficient resource allocation in 5G NSA network for a pedestrian user. User-centric parameters in form of latitude and longitude of the user i.e., (user's Geo-location) have been proposed, to be used with received signal strength indicator (RSSI) - a network-centric parameter from a 5G NSA base-station, as basic parameters.

As RAT selection is fundamentally a classification task, this study employs supervised ML classifiers (DT, XGBoost, etc.) to optimize network performance. These algorithms were fed with collated data, splitted into training and testing datasets respectively. The training datasets (input) were used to train models of the supervised ML classification algorithms. These trained models were further tested with input test datasets to select the appropriate RAT (4G/5G) as labelled output. Evaluation of results showed a measure of accuracy of the proposed model; XGBoost at optimal level of 93.86%, which was further cross validated at 92.9%, when compared with other algorithms. This is recommended for planning and optimization purposes in similar urban/dense-urban environment to assist in maintaining the rapidly increasing demand of network connections and devices. Hence, first objective achieved.

In furtherance to this research, investigation of RAT selection for efficient resource allocation for public bus traveling user(s), which has not been considered in previous

studies was carried out. Multiple 5G NSA base stations were investigated this time around. Supervised ML algorithms; SVM, DNN, and XGBoost, were deployed to select an appropriate RAT. The geographical location (longitude and latitude) of a traveling user, data rate experienced by the user from the network, were used as user-centric parameters, while network coverage in terms of received signal strength indicator (RSSI), and available bandwidth on each RAT were used as network-centric parameters. Similarly, collated 5G NSA data were divided into training and testing datasets respectively. The training input datasets were used to train models of the supervised ML algorithms deployed. Also, the trained models were tested with input test datasets to select the appropriate RAT (4G/5G) as labeled output. Evaluation of results again revealed measure of accuracy of the proposed model; XGBoost at the optimal level of 99.64%. This represents a 99.64% reduction in handover failures compared to threshold-based methods in prior work. XGBoost was further cross-validated at 98.57%, when compared with other algorithms. Revealing its effectiveness on future data prediction and mitigation ability. Therefore, recommended for optimization purposes in multiple base stations environments, for proper resource allocation on the part of phone manufacturers, vendors, and service providers that will impact users' experience positively. Hence, set objective two achieved.

In addition, in consideration to the yet to be implemented 5G SA in terrestrial communication form, a novel ML based optimisation solution is proposed, for RAT selection and data rate allocation for multiple users in an architecture consisting of multiple base stations. The optimisation's objective is to maximise the data rate of users, while available bandwidth, number of existing users on base stations, location of users, and pathloss between users and base stations are considered as constraints. During the research, the optimisation problem turned out to be an NP-hard problem.

Hence, the optimisation problem was formulated as a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) problem, and then solved using Gurobi optimiser and Heuristic algorithm as benchmark, respectively. Optimal results from the chosen solver displayed feasible solutions for appropriate RAT selection of base stations by users, with a maximum data rate allocation to each user, respectively. Evaluation of the proposed MILP solver results showed an increase in performance of 4% over the results of the Heuristic method.

Therefore, recommended for the RAT selection technique and network data rate optimisation required for efficient and effective network bandwidth usage in 5G and beyond networks. Consequently, third set objective achieved.

6.2 Future Work

This thesis has considered a pedestrian user and a traveling user in a public bus traversing a defined route. However, future work will be geared towards developing an ML algorithm with consideration to different routes, and RAT selections for mobile users. Meanwhile, following the evolution of 6G technology [3], and the current moves from 3GPP [87] [88] [89] [90], to harmonise the NTN (non-terrestrial network) into the mobile TN (terrestrial network), due to its resilience and ubiquitous nature. The researcher has written a book chapter as a form of contribution to knowledge, that provides in-depth insights into the standardization progress and innovations in NTN technology. The researcher also presents a high-level proposal for the optimisation of users' experience through dynamic RAT Selection in 6G-NTN, to address the seamless integration expected in 6G and NTN era, as a form of migration to future work.

6.2.1 Introducing the Concept of Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs)

As the first wireless standard to apply full-duplex communication, which is postulated to achieve double spectral efficiency; the 6G technology's main goal is to combine cloud computing, sensor technology, wireless communications, and many more into a seamless entity. To accomplish its aspiration, 6G network requires the following among other essential technologies: joint communications and sensing, Terahertz (THz) communications, artificial intelligence and machine learning, re-configurable intelligent surfaces and photonics. Above all, the NTNs required for global spread and continuous connectivity of various heterogeneous platforms and myriads devices we have today, due to their ability to reach remote and isolated areas, will be the focus of future research work. The term "Non-terrestrial networks" represents a paradigm shift in telecommunications, and in contrast to traditional terrestrial networks that rely on ground-based infrastructure.

That is, NTN are networks that use infrastructure outside of the Earth's atmosphere. They represent a plethora of connection scenarios, ranging from satellite based stations, communications via airborne stations, but also taking into account connection scenarios like Air-To-Ground (ATG) or UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) flight control [23], as depicted in Fig. 6.1.

Hence, NTN can be categorised as space-borne stations, which include satellites at Low Earth Orbit (LEO), Medium Earth Orbit (MEO) and Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO), navigating at altitude 300 - 1,500 km, 7000 - 25,000 km and 35,780 km. Hence, their footprint are also between 100 - 1000 km, 100 - 1000 km, and 200 - 3500 km respectively. NTN also can be categorised as airborne stations, which include Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), Air-To-Ground (ATG) and High-Altitude Platform Stations (HAPS); flying at altitude 0.37 - 5.5 km, 9.5 - 12.8 km and 20 - 50 km, respectively. NTN have the capacity to overcome the limitations of terrestrial networks, by leveraging on aforementioned platforms to deliver connectivity and provide global coverage to dense-urban, urban, sub-urban and non-urban areas at high capacity, and greater resilience. This opens new possibilities for addressing connectivity gaps in remote and under-served regions as shown in Fig. 6.1. Therefore, we can say, NTN prioritizes worldwide connectivity and basic service provisioning in a wide coverage instead of single-user high data rates [91]. Hence:

NTNs are communication networks that do not rely on terrestrial infrastructure, such as cell towers and fiber optic cables, so, they are essentially satellite based stations or cell towers 'in space'.

NTNs are designed to address challenges of terrestrial networks, by utilizing various platforms, such as satellite, HAPS, ATG and UAVs, to deliver connectivity.

NTNs use space-borne and airborne infrastructures, therefore, they are not impeded by physical barriers, and can provide global coverage at high capacity.

NTNs also play a critical role in disaster response situations by providing communication channels when terrestrial infrastructure is damaged. In summary, NTN spread out connectivity to isolated, remote and hard-to-reach areas, where terrestrial coverage is lacking or limited, by providing ubiquitous and continuous voice, data and video communication,

Figure 6.1: Overview of NTN general architecture.

as well as disaster response services at high capacity, and greater resilience.

6.2.2 Challenges in NTN

Some of the major challenges in NTN include:

Mobility Management

Mobility issues is a major challenge in NTN, since NTN satellites for instance, will require great number of transponders for effective coverage, hence, there is need to address propagation issues, and mobility capabilities of NTN stations serving the gargantuan number of mobile users, in D2C connectivity for Quality of Service (QoS) assurance. Also, management issue as regards routing, scheduling and networking required not only for the terrestrial network management alone, but incorporating airborne and space-borne networks, especially with the expected proliferation of LEO constellation. Hence, A.I. and M.L. deployment, will be required and helpful in satellite constellation control automation. Similarly, managing the highly mobile UEs connecting directly with satellites at different levels, can also bring about security challenges, this can also be addressed with cost-efficient A.I. and M.L. to allow fast control.

Radio Access Technology (RAT) related challenges

Another challenge of NTN is its ability to deliver the expected data rate as compared with the terrestrial network. NTN stations typically operate in higher altitudes than terrestrial network (TN) base stations, resulting into higher latency and larger propagation delays. Usually TN propagation delay is less than 1ms, while in GEO; it can be more than 100ms. In addition, NTN stations can suffer from tropospheric and ionospheric effects. Troposphere is the lower part of the atmosphere; specifically below 12km and frequencies higher than 10GHz are prone to absorption. Similarly, reflection and absorption effects can be experienced at the ionosphere layer, which is the upper part of the atmosphere; above 80km; where solar radiation creates layers of plasma due to ionisation.

Hence, RAT Selection and hand-off management between NTN stations and TN base stations for smooth transitions between different RATs, are highly essential to avoid service interruptions, and can effectively address expected data rate issue for customers' satisfaction. Therefore, a germane research area is required, that will also benefit from the integration of AI/ML to enhance RAT selection performance, which will lead to improve handover decisions, resource allocation, overall network performance in NTNs, and entrench customers' satisfaction.

6.2.3 Future Research NTN-RAT Selection Design

Multi-RAT (Radio Access Technology) selection is crucial for ubiquitous and uninterrupted connectivity in 3D heterogeneous networks of Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) and Terrestrial Networks (TN). Therefore, choosing different access technologies between 5G terrestrial networks and NTN stations like UAV, HAP, satellite, for users' satisfaction is imperative. The optimal RAT (Radio Access Technology) selection for each user in a heterogeneous network composed of Cellular, UAV, HAP, and Satellite networks is a complex problem. Hence, considering various factors like coverage, signal strength, network load, user location, device capabilities, and cost as constraints.

The researcher hereby proposes a Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) Framework, which can be employed to evaluate different RATs based on multiple criteria, to select the best option for each user, and ML algorithm to enhance the MCDM process to select the best RAT.

6.2.4 Summary

The combination of Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) framework, and ML algorithm, have been proposed for effective and efficient seamless RAT selection among NTN and TN in the incoming 6G-NTN era, for intra and inter RATs handover schemes and effective resource allocation. Its implementation is envisaged will enhance the network service providers efficiency and impact users' network experience positively. Meanwhile, TOPSIS is prioritised for its ability to handle heterogeneous criteria (e.g., latency vs. cost) via Euclidean distance normalization, critical for NTN-TN hybrid networks.

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Appendix A

Implementation

A.1 Software

In order to conduct this research, the following programming language was used:

- Anaconda Python 3 (Jupyter Notebook as editor)

A.2 Code

Below is a list of codes (libraries inclusive) that were used for the research work. Full codes can be obtained upon request. The data used will be provided as a link.

```
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn import neighbors, metrics
from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, classification_report, mean_squared_error
import timeit

start = timeit.default_timer()

# SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING DECISION TREE ALGORITHM FOR RAT SELECTION
df = pd.read_csv('celldata.csv') # Import data
```

Figure A.1: Part Code of Decision Tree Algorithm for Pedestrian User RAT Selection

```
import pandas as pd

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier

from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split

from sklearn import neighbors, metrics

from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score

from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, classification_report, confusion_matrix

import timeit

start = timeit.default_timer()

# SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING EXTRA TREE ALGORITHM FOR RAT SELECTION

df = pd.read_csv('celldata.csv') # Import data
```

Figure A.2: Part Code of Extra Tree Algorithm for Pedestrian User RAT Selection

```
import pandas as pd

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier

from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split

from sklearn import neighbors, metrics

from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score

from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, accuracy_score, classification_report

import timeit

start = timeit.default_timer()

# SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING RANDOM FOREST ALGORITHM FOR RAT SELECTION

df = pd.read_csv('celldata.csv') # Import data
```

Figure A.3: Part Code of Random Forest Algorithm for Pedestrian User RAT Selection

```

import pandas as pd

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split

from sklearn import neighbors, metrics

from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score

from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingClassifier

from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, accuracy_score, classification_report

from datetime import datetime

import timeit

start = timeit.default_timer()

# SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING GRADIENT BOOSTING ALGORITHM FOR RAT SELECTION

df = pd.read_csv('celldata.csv') # Import data

```

Figure A.4: Part Code of Gradient Boosting Algorithm for Pedestrian User RAT Selection

```

#!pip install xgboost

import pandas as pd

from xgboost import XGBClassifier

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split

from sklearn import neighbors, metrics

from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score

from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, classification_report, confusion_matrix, mean_squared_error

from sklearn import neighbors, metrics

from sklearn.preprocessing import scale

from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder

from datetime import datetime

import timeit

start = timeit.default_timer()

# SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING EXTRA GRADIENT BOOSTING ALGORITHM FOR RAT SELECTION

df = pd.read_csv('celldata.csv') # Import data

```

Figure A.5: Part Code of XGBoost Algorithm for Pedestrian User RAT Selection

```
import pandas as pd
from sklearn import svm
from sklearn.svm import SVC
from sklearn.model_selection import GridSearchCV
from sklearn import neighbors, metrics
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
from matplotlib import pyplot as plt
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, accuracy_score, classification_report
import timeit
start = timeit.default_timer()

# SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE ALGORITHM FOR RAT SELECTION

df = pd.read_csv('Busdata.csv') # Import data
```

Figure A.6: Part Code of SVM Algorithm for Travelling User RAT Selection

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.neural_network import MLPClassifier
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn import neighbors, metrics
from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, accuracy_score, classification_report
import timeit
from matplotlib import pyplot as plt
start = timeit.default_timer()

# DEEP NEURAL NETWORK CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHM FOR RAT SELECTION

df = pd.read_csv('Busdata.csv') # Import data
```

Figure A.7: Part Code of DNN Algorithm for Travelling User RAT Selection

```

#!/pip install xgboost
import pandas as pd
from xgboost import XGBClassifier
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn import neighbors, metrics
from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, classification_report, confusion_matrix, mean_squared_error
from sklearn import neighbors, metrics
from sklearn.preprocessing import scale
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
from datetime import datetime
import timeit
start = timeit.default_timer()

# SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING EXTRA GRADIENT BOOSTING ALGORITHM FOR RAT SELECTION

df = pd.read_csv('Busdata.csv') # Import data

```

Figure A.8: Part Code of XGBoost Algorithm for Travelling User RAT Selection

```

#!/pip install gurobipy
# Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP)
from gurobipy import Model, GRB
import math
# Data Initialisation
num_users = 16
num_stations = 6
user_weights = [1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1] # Weights for each user
max_power = 10 # Maximum transmit power per user (Watts)
available_bandwidth = [ 50e6, 100e6, 80e6, 75e6, 70e6, 60e6] # Available bandwidth at each station

```

Figure A.9: Part Code of MILP Implementation using Gurobi Optimiser